

Modernisation of DC-DC converter topologies for solar energy harvesting applications: A review

Tole Sutikno^{1,2}, Hendril Satrian Purnama², Rizky Ajie Aprilianto², Awang Jusoh³,
Nuryono Satya Widodo¹, Budi Santosa⁴

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Embedded System and Power Electronic Research Group (ESPERG), Yogyakarta, Indonesia

³School of Electrical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia

⁴Department of Vocational Teacher Education, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 2, 2022

Revised Oct 11, 2022

Accepted Oct 17, 2022

Keyword:

Converter topology

DC-DC converter

Energy harvesting

Renewable energy

Solar photovoltaic

ABSTRACT

Solar photovoltaic (PV) power generation has grown in popularity as a renewable energy source due to the numerous advantages it provides. These advantages include the ease with which it may be assigned, the absence of noise, the longer life, the absence of pollution, the shorter installation time, the high mobility and portability of its parts, and the ability of its output power to satisfy peak load needs. DC-DC converters are commonly used in solar energy harvesting systems because they enable more efficient usage of solar cells. One of the challenges is selecting an appropriate converter, which has an impact on the operation of the PV system. The modernization of various distinct DC-DC converter topologies for solar energy harvesting systems is discussed in this article. Boost, buck-boost, single-ended primary-inductance converter (SEPIC), Cuk, Zeta, and Z-source are some of these topologies. The topologies have been compared in order to provide extensive information on the hardware complexity, implementation cost, efficiency of the energy transfer elements, tracking efficiency, and converter efficiency. This paper will be useful as a handy reference in choosing the best converter topology for solar energy harvesting applications.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Tole Sutikno

Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Industrial Technology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan

South Ringroad st., Tamanan, Banguntapan, Bantul Regency, Special Region of Yogyakarta 55191

Indonesia

Email: tole@te.uad.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of the huge increase in the extraction of fossil fuels, which has a negative influence on the environment, it has become increasingly desirable to employ renewable energy sources. It motivates a large number of researchers to devote more effort to researching renewable energy sources (RES). Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology is becoming increasingly popular in power plants for a variety of reasons, including the fact that these plants have a significantly longer lifespan, are less harmful to the environment, require less maintenance, and can generate more power to meet the demands of various loads. The most essential aspect is that solar energy is really renewable. It is available every day and can be used anywhere in the world. This solar energy harvesting technology is becoming more popular as an alternative to fossil-fuel-generated electricity. A solar water heater is an excellent example of a solar energy harvesting application that is widely used in sunny climates around the world [1]–[22].

Power electronic interfaces or power converters, such as DC-DC converters, are required to convert the low DC output voltage from a solar PV energy harvesting system to the voltage rating required by any suitable utilization voltage. The topologies of DC-DC converters are intended to fulfill the specific demands of DC loads. There are numerous types of DC-DC converters that can operate as switching-mode regulators, regulating the unregulated DC voltage with conversion to an appropriate utilization voltage by increasing or reducing the value of the DC output voltage. Each converter requires a power switching device to turn on and off as needed. In addition, load matching and increased power output from the PV systems should be possible with the usage of DC-DC converters in conjunction with maximum power point tracking (MPPT) [16], [22]–[43].

However, the low DC output voltages that are generated by the PV array are subject to a wide range of variables, such as solar irradiation, sudden shifts caused by the effects of shadowing, ambient temperature, the cleanliness degree of the PV module surface, mismatching of PV modules, and a number of other factors. These variables can have a significant impact on the low DC output voltages that are generated by the PV array. Diverse power electronic DC–DC converters are developed so that this issue may be resolved, as well as so that a steady output voltage may be provided. The DC–DC converter has been around since the 1920s and was designed specifically for use with solar PV systems. It is an extremely important requirement that a DC-DC boost converter be developed in order to regulate the low and irregular DC output voltage coming from the PV arrays [7], [9], [44]–[46].

In recent years, the DC-DC converter has become an increasingly important component of systems that collect solar energy. It delivers a voltage that is better suitable for a wide variety of applications that use photovoltaic panels as the source [46]–[113]. When selecting DC-DC converters, it is important to take into consideration a number of different criteria, including high efficiency, high reliability, low conduction loss, economic viability, and low switching loss. As a direct consequence of this, researchers all around the world are consistently working on the creation of DC-DC converter topologies [114]–[118]. This paper provides a wider range of options for selecting DC-DC converters that are appropriate for a variety of power conversion applications. The tendency toward modernization of the DC-DC converter that is used for solar energy harvesting systems is the topic of discussion that is carried out in this study. It is connected to the topological structure, which includes both the benefits and the drawbacks. Additionally, a comparison of topologies is carried out in order to provide particular information and future research work linked to the development of DC-DC converters for solar energy harvesting systems. This comparison is carried out in order to offer specific information.

2. STRUCTURE OF A SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEM

Energy harvesting is the process of obtaining useful electrical power by gathering and transforming the energy that is already present in the surrounding environment from various sources. One of the interesting and potentially fruitful solutions to meet the ever-increasing energy demands of the globe is to collect energy from the sun. The total system for collecting solar energy is made up of a variety of different devices and components, including as PV arrays, MPPT controllers, DC-DC converters, batteries, loads (both AC and DC), and inverters [9], [11], [12], [16], [17], [58], [119], [120]. The comprehensive schematic block of the solar energy collecting system is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of a solar photovoltaic energy harvesting system

Solar energy is converted or harvested by the solar photovoltaic array and then converted into electrical energy. To produce a more usable power output, the output is transmitted to the DC-DC converter. This component converts the PV-produced variable DC voltage into a fixed voltage that is proportionate to the load requirements. The MPPT controller simultaneously works to achieve MPP conversion from PV and provide a pulse width modulation (PWM) signal to drive the DC-DC converter's switching mechanism [22], [23], [25], [27], [28], [32], [38], [39], [42], [43], [52], [77], [81], [93], [94], [98], [108], [112], [121]–[146]. These two processes happen simultaneously. The output of the DC-DC converter may then either be connected to the inverter device, at which time it can either be connected to the grid or provide an AC load, or it can be used to supply load sides such as batteries or DC loads [21], [25], [38], [43], [50], [60], [88], [95], [107], [128], [147], [148].

2.1. Mathematical model of PV cell

The output current of the module (I_{pv}) may be calculated using Kirchhoff's Current law, as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 depicts the I-V parameters of a solar cell. The I-V characteristics (the operating points of the PV generator) are affected by the load conductance:

$$I_{pv} = n_p I_L - I_d - \frac{V_d}{R_{sh}} \tag{1}$$

where I_d represents the diode current, I_L represents the light-generated current, n_p represents the number of cells connected in parallel, R_{sh} represents the shunt resistance and V_d represents the diode voltage. The diode current is denoted as:

$$I_d = n_p I_{os} \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(v + I_{cell} R_s)}{n_s A K T} \right] - 1 \right\} \tag{2}$$

where A represents the diode's ideality constant, I_{os} represents the reverse saturation current, k represents the Boltzmann's constant, n_s represents the cells connected number in series, q represents the electron charge, R_s represents the series resistance, T represents the cell temperature in Kelvin, and v represents the module's output voltage. When (2) is substituted for (1), the result:

$$I_{pv} = n_p I_{os} \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(v + I_{cell} R_s)}{n_s A K T} \right] - 1 \right\} - \frac{V_d}{R_{sh}} \tag{3}$$

the mathematical model is built using the preceding equations [149], [150]. The maker of a PV module gives reference values for defined operating circumstances, such as standard test condition (STC). The light produced current (I_L) is affected by temperature and irradiance offer the equation for I_L [151], [152].

$$I_L = \frac{\phi}{\phi_{ref}} [I_{Lref} + \mu I_{sc} (T - T_{ref})] \tag{4}$$

Where I_{Lref} represents the light current at the reference condition, T_{ref} represents the reference temperature, ϕ represents the irradiance, ϕ_{ref} represents the reference irradiance, and μI_{sc} represents the manufacturer supplied temperature coefficient of the short-circuit current. I_{Lref} and μI_{sc} are given in a manufacturer's data sheet. In [10], the reverse saturation current I_{os} is reported:

$$I_{os} = D_f T^3 \exp \left(\frac{-qE}{AKT} \right) \tag{5}$$

where D_f represents the diode diffusion factor, and E represents the band gap energy at 300 K. (1.12 eV for Si, 1.35 eV for GaAs) [153].

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the output of a photovoltaic cell under conditions of an irradiation of 500 W/m² and a temperature of 323 K, respectively. These results are derived from (3) through (5). The impact of temperature change with constant irradiance was tested by setting the irradiance value to 500 W/m² and adjusting the temperature to 323 K, 360 K, and 373 K. These temperatures were chosen so that the effect could be studied [154].

Figure 2. Circuit diagram of PV model [150]

Figure 3. I-V Characteristics of solar cell with load line [150]

Figure 4. P-V characteristics of PV cell [150]

Figure 5. I-V characteristics of PV cell [150]

2.2 Maximum power point tracking (MPPT)

The operating point shifts depending on the amount of available sunlight and load. In order to make greater use of PV systems, the PV system needs to be able to perform at its optimal efficiency regardless of changes in the amount of available sunlight and the load being applied [155]. The maximum power point is the one and only location along the P–V curve at which the output power is at its highest value (MPP). Solar tracking is the traditional way that is utilized to get the most out of the energy that is collected [156][157]. One other approach that may be taken to get maximum power is called MPPT [6]–[8], [11], [12], [15], [19], [27], [28], [35], [41], [42], [48], [51], [52], [57], [62], [64]–[66], [69]–[71], [74], [77], [80], [82], [83], [85], [89], [90], [93], [95], [96], [98], [106], [108], [112], [113], [158]–[245]. The MPP can be detected with the use of an MPPT algorithm that is placed on the microcontroller [246]. This circumstance is depicted in Figure 1, which is a block diagram. Following the MPPT controller's successful tracking of the MPP, a triggering signal is sent to the converter switches. By changing the duty ratio, the load impedance may be adjusted and brought into alignment with the ideal internal impedance [247].

The PV current varies dramatically as the weather changes. MPPT needs quick dynamic action to follow the operational range if current is employed as a fixed variable. The change in voltage, on the other hand, is limited to 70-80% of V_{oc} . As a result, PV voltage is often used as a control variable [248]. MPPT is based on measuring PV power and regulating PV voltage. The ratio of the input and output voltages can be suitably changed by altering the duty cycle of the converter [249], [250]. Numerous methods are utilized on a regular basis to accomplish the task of tracking maximum power point in PV systems [185]. These methods include hill-climbing, perturbation and observation (P&O), look-up table, incremental conductance (Inc-Cond), linearization-based, DC-link capacitor droop control, curve fitting, extremum seeking control, feedback voltage or current, feedback of power variation with voltage, feedback of power variation with current, firefly algorithm, fractional open-circuit voltage (FOCV), fractional short-circuit current (FSCI), artificial neural network (ANN), fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimization (PSO), ant colony based optimization, one cycle control (OCC), ripple correlation control (RCC), parasitic capacitance, and sliding-mode [6]–[8], [11], [12], [15], [19], [27], [28], [35], [41], [42], [48], [51], [52], [57], [62], [64]–[66], [69]–[71], [74], [77], [80], [82], [83], [85], [89], [90], [93], [95], [96], [98], [106], [108], [112], [113], [158]–[245].

In recent years, a variety of methodologies have been developed to monitor MPP in PV systems. The combination of ANN and the P&O algorithm is one of the available approaches [52], [174], [239]. This approach can determine the MPP in a short amount of time under a variety of weather conditions since it does not require costly irradiance sensors [251]. On the other hand, significant negatives include greater power oscillations and a complicated installation. Another technique for locating the MPP, this one utilizing current sweeping and analyzed by Tsang *et al.* [252]. The controller for this approach does a significant amount of mathematical work. Mohanty *et al.* devised the grey wolf optimization in order to gather the greatest amount of electricity from the PV systems while they were partially shaded. The findings of the simulation are analyzed and contrasted with those of the P&O and enhanced particle swarm optimization (PSO) methods [3], [6], [14], [26], [34], [70], [212], [214], [253], [254]. The results of the tests demonstrated that the grey wolf optimization works better than traditional algorithms in terms of tracking speed, ripple content, and extraction efficiency [255]. Wang *et al.* [256] describe an MPPT approach that is appropriate for long PV string. By narrowing the searching voltage range, rapid global MPPT, also known as R-GMPPT, is able to make tracking faster. Next comes the skipping and judgment procedure, which is followed by the lowering in the voltage range. Misjudging, on the other hand, can have an effect on how well the algorithm works.

3. CONVERTER TOPOLOGIES

In PV installations, DC-DC converters are provided so that solar cells may be utilized as effectively as possible [257]. In the vast majority of converters used in the solar energy sector, power semiconductor components like MOSFET and IGBT are heavily utilized. With a limiting voltage of up to 1.2 kV, the high voltage converter switches have a switching frequency of higher than 10 kHz. Despite the fact that the switching frequency of a high voltage converter is restricted to about one thousand hertz (kHz), due to increased switching loss. This restriction on the switching frequency was alleviated because to developments in the technology used in the fabrication of switching devices. Anthon *et al.* [258] demonstrated a high-power boost converter that runs at frequencies up to 300 kHz and uses a normally-on SiC JFET as the switching device. Utilizing a MOSFET that has a low drain-source on resistance is one way to cut down significantly on the amount of conduction loss [259]. The capacity to sustain output regardless of any fluctuations in input is the primary criterion for selecting DC-DC converters in photovoltaic (PV) systems. Other important considerations are cost, efficiency, and energy flow. It is important that the effect of voltage ripple on the output side of the PV module be as small as feasible [186].

The difficulty of the hardware involved in the converter comes from a number of aspects, including the choosing of the filter size and the gate driving circuit. When compared to the other converters, the single-

ended primary-inductance converter, also known as the SEPIC, has a higher output voltage ripple on the output side. The results of a comparison of the hardware requirements, costs, and efficiencies of several types of converters are presented in Table 1. These converters include boost, buck-boost, SEPIC, Cuk, Zeta, and Z-source. Calculating the effectiveness of a converter, $\eta_{converter}$ requires using the (6). The tracking efficiency may be expressed as a ratio between the power at the panel's terminals and the panel's maximum possible output of power, denoted by $P_{pv\ max}$ [260]. The (7) that measures extraction may also be used to track efficiency $\eta_{extraction}$.

$$\eta_{converter} = \frac{V_{out} * I_{out}}{v * I_{pv}} = \frac{(v * I_{pv}) - P_{losses}}{v * I_{pv}} \quad (6)$$

$$\eta_{extraction} = \frac{v * I_{pv}}{P_{pv\ max}} \quad (7)$$

where V_{out} represents the voltage of the converter at the output side, I_{out} represents the output current of the converter, v represents the voltage at the output of the panel, I_{pv} represents the current at the output of the panel, and P_{losses} represents the losses of the converter.

In renewable energy systems, the non-isolated topologies of converters have been studied in many papers and can be simplified into the category depicted in Figure 6. Although SEPIC, buck-boost, and Cuk converters have a significant ripple in the load current, these converters provide a great deal of leeway in terms of the output voltage they may produce. In contrast to these other topologies, the buck topology has a significant current ripple [261]. There is no way to combine the inductor into the filter and converter to make a single magnetic core for the buck and boost converters. When contrasted with SEPIC and Cuk, these converters produce a tremendous amount of output [262]. Because the output voltage of the PV array is always lower than the voltage of the grid, buck converters are almost never utilized in the role of DC-DC converters. A large capacitor is necessary in order to smooth out the array current since the current output from the array to the converter comprises significant current spikes. In their study on PV systems, Taghvaei *et al.* [263] studied the qualities of boost, buck-boost, SEPIC, Cuk, Zeta, and Z-source converters. Even if the input current has severe ripple and noise problems, the buck-boost converter is the one that is able to attain the greatest performance out of all of these converters. This is the case regardless of the environment or the load.

When the duty ratio changes from 0 to 1, the load resistance (R_L) determines how much the buck converter's input resistance shifts toward infinity. If the input resistance is the same as R_{opt} , the system will function at the MPP setting, as shown in Figure 3. Therefore, MPP tracking is not achievable in buck converters when the resistance of the load is larger than R_{opt} . When the duty ratio changes from 0 to 1, the boost converter's input resistance shifts from 0 to load resistance. This happens vice versa. Because of this, MPP tracking cannot occur if the load resistance is lower than the R_{opt} value. When the duty ratio changes from 0 to 1, the buck boost converter's input resistance might be anywhere from 0 to infinite, depending on the setting. Because of this, buck-boost converters are capable of achieving MPP regardless of the magnitude of the load resistance [117], [270], [273], [276].

Figure 6. Non-isolated DC-DC converter category

Table 1. Comparison of various converters

Converter Topology	Hardware Complexity	Production Cost	Average Tracking Efficiency	Efficiency of the Converter	Energy Transfer Elements
Boost	L	L	L	H	<i>L</i>
Buck-Boost	M	L	H	M	<i>L</i>
SEPIC	H	M	H	M	<i>LC</i>
Cuk	M	M	H	M	<i>C</i>
Zeta	H	M	H	H	<i>LC</i>
Z-source	H	M	H	H	<i>LC</i>
References	[264], [265]	[118], [265], [266]	[267]–[270]	[148], [265], [271]–[273]	[118], [261], [274], [275]

L: Low, M: Medium, H: High, *L*: Inductor, *C*: Capacitor, *LC*: Inductor and Capacitor

PV applications also make use of advanced converters such as the Luo converter (Ultra-lift and Positive-output super-lift), the KY boost converter, and the quadratic boost converter [276]. However, research on the use of these converters in PV systems is still in its early stages. Kumar *et al.* [277] explored the construction of a negative output elementary Luo converter that is utilized to produce MPP with the assistance of an Inc-Cond MPPT method. Ghamrawi *et al.* [45], [278] investigated the effect that include MPPT in the control strategy has on the stability of a quadratic double boost converter that also captures MPP. This is suitable for use in systems that work in essentially constant weather conditions, such as solar applications in space, and it is an appropriate application for use in such systems. Sivakumar *et al.* [279] investigated the achievement of buck-boost, Cuk, SEPIC, ultra-lift Luo, and positive-output super-lift Luo converters. The mathematical modeling of state space was introduced. When compared to alternative topologies, the scientists found that ultra-lift and super-lift Luo converters suffer from substantial power loss in the diode. Tomaszuk and Krupa [280] investigated high-efficiency converter topologies for renewable applications in depth.

In yet another technical evaluation of DC-DC converters using MPPT, Hossain *et al.* [281] examined the performance of several types of converters, including their control applications. Khosrogorji *et al.* [282] investigated current advances in magnetic and electric multi-input converters. Neng *et al.* [283] offered an overview of three-port DC-DC converters that meet the condition of two inputs and one output. It is possible to connect one input to the output of the solar panel. The battery can be linked to the system using the second input. The output port is able to establish a connection to the grid. When opposed to their isolated counterparts, three-port converters that are not isolated can have benefits such as cheaper costs and higher levels of dependability. In the review [45], the non-isolated DC-DC converters that are chosen for MPPT of PV systems together with their selection criteria were the primary emphasis. In their study, Zhang *et al.* [284] looked at the challenges that traditional voltage source and current source converters face, such as lower output gain and shoot-through. The authors came to the conclusion that the impedance source converters are capable of overcoming these difficulties. When the equivalent impedance approaches infinity, the impedance-source converter is classified as a current source converter. When the equivalent value of the impedance approaches the null point, the impedance-source converter is deemed to be the same as a voltage source converter.

In order to conduct an in-depth analysis of the properties of the converter, modeling of the converter is carried out. A number of different approaches, including state space averaging (SSA), circuit averaging, and decomposition of Fourier series, can be utilized in the process of circuit modeling. As a result of the incorporation of Fourier series study into a mathematical model, the capability of applying control rules is constrained when using Fourier series decomposition. In the process of designing the feedback-control loop for DC-DC converters, a simple signal model can be of great assistance. When constructing the power stage of converters, circuit averaging and SSA are two methods that are utilized [285].

4. MODERNISATION OF DC-DC CONVERTER TOPOLOGIES FOR SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING

In this section, the modernization of DC-DC converters in terms of non-isolated step-up configuration for solar harvesting energy applications, such as boost, buck-boost, SEPIC, Cuk, Zeta, and Z-source, are presented.

4.1. Boost converter

The voltage on the load side is larger than the PV voltage in solar harvesting energy applications. It implies that the step-up voltage procedure must be carried out, and the boost converter becomes one of the several topologies that may be chosen and included into an MPPT [32], [36], [55], [58], [78], [81], [82], [93], [102], [103], [110], [132], [135], [258], [264], [276], [278], [286]–[300]. The boost converter is the most popular option, and it has been manufactured by industry [295]. Several improvements have been proposed by researchers to increase boost converter performance. Huber and Jovanovic [301] investigated the use of a cascade structure to boost voltage gain while decreasing ripples. The initial stage of the cascaded structure has

minimal voltage stress and may function at a high switching frequency due to the low input voltage. The second component runs at a lower switching frequency, which reduces switching losses. However, the disadvantages include a cascaded topology structure with a greater circuit components number, EMI noise and reduced efficiency.

A linked a switched capacitor and inductor can be utilized to augment a boost converter's voltage gain. A connected inductor, as opposed to two separate inductors, can employ a single magnetic core. As a result, it offers benefits such as lower magnetic loss and ripple content. The leakage inductance of the coupled inductor assists in decreasing output-diode reverse-recovery difficulties. However, the increased switching loss and current stress are substantial drawbacks. To decrease voltage spikes at MOSFET switches, a lossless passive clamp circuit is provided [302]. Lin *et al.* [303] and Wu *et al.* [304] advocated three-level boost converters because they achieve higher voltage gain with less voltage stress than two-level boost converters. In typical interleaved boost converters, current ripples and voltage stresses in switches are considerable.

An interleaved DC-DC converter was constructed by Li *et al.* [305] utilizing winding cross-coupled inductors (WCCIs). These inductors have three winding coupled inductors, one of which links to the other phase of the converter. Active clamping is a technology that can give zero voltage transmission (ZVT) performance while also considerably lowering switching losses. This can be accomplished through the use of an active clamp. In spite of the fact that an LLC resonant converter has a limited DC voltage gain range, using one helps achieve zero switching, reduced electromagnetic interference (EMI), and good efficiency. Xiaofeng *et al.* [296] studied a two-phase interleaved step-up converter paired with a current-fed LLC (IBI-LLC) resonant converter. A fixed-frequency PWM control reduces circulating current, generates ripple-free input current, and achieves load independence. The resonant frequency is continually tuned into the switching frequency f_s . The resonant tank circuit's input voltage is achieved by matching the resonant frequency with the switching frequency f_s . The duty cycle is regulated to a very narrow range about 0.5, resulting in operating points in the middle of the range, which assures optimal performance to a large part for PV applications because MPP are often placed in the middle of voltage values. The resonant inductor and capacitor control the gain characteristics, whilst boost inductors and behavior inductance impact the zero-voltage switching (ZVS) circumstances. Setting the maximum and lowest gain settings yields the L_r and C_r values. Magnetizing inductors and boost inductors are computed using the current under ZVS and gain for known values of L_r and C_r for various combinations of quality factor and duty ratio.

Hung *et al.* [297] proposed a unique strategy for improving boost converter efficiency and lowering output voltage ripple. Their article examined the functioning of a converter in DCM with pulse frequency modulation (PFM) under the premise that PV systems provide relatively little power at low irradiance. When the switching frequency is reduced, the ripple content increases. This constraint is overcome by adjusting the turn on period based on the inductor current's peak value. Due to the size of passive parts and finite commutation periods, the conversion ratio of a PV system that requires a high-gain converter is limited. A step-up transformer can be used to remedy this problem, but it has limitations such as lower frequency and severe switching transients. A connected inductor can be used as a workaround. However, a big capacitance capacitor is necessary to avoid significant input current ripple. MPPT gain is restricted due to the possibility of MPP deviation at higher input voltage levels. Haroun *et al.* [306] used a two-stage technique to build a cascade connection of two boost converters, whose function is identical to that of loss-free resistors. Pires *et al.* [307] studied a boost-self lift Cuk DC-DC converter with increased voltage gain suitable for half bridge transformers with low VSI. This converter enables a direct connection between the solar panel and the grid's neutral wire. The incremental conductance MPPT algorithm governs the duty cycle, D . The equation for voltage gain, V_o/V_i , is provided by (8).

$$\frac{V_o}{V_i} = \frac{2}{1-D} \quad (8)$$

4.2. Buck-boost converter

In comparison to boost converters, buck-boost converters have the ability to cover the whole I-V characteristics. Additionally, when buck-boost converters operate in continuous conduction mode (CCM), the input current is smooth and continuous with very little ripple. The voltage and current stress placed on components by two-switch buck-boost converters is significantly lower than that of single-switch buck-boost converters [22], [42], [53], [81], [87], [97], [102], [103], [115], [117], [119], [125], [133], [138], [142], [146], [164], [168], [222], [225], [263], [264], [266], [288], [289], [308]–[320]. Ahmed *et al.* [315] present a two-switch non-inverting buck-boost converter with the possibility for extra current storage. To track MPP, a P&O MPPT algorithm-based approach is utilized. The experimental findings reveal that the suggested converter has a greater efficiency under large loads. Depending on the condition of the immediate input voltage in respect to

the output voltage, the system can function in one of two modes: either a PWM-controlled buck or a boost. Both of these modes are possible.

Samavatian *et al.* [321] used a magnetically connected input-output inductor to simulate an interleaved buck-boost converter. The SSA approach was used in the analysis. The dampening network minimizes active-switch voltage stress while interleaved approaches improve converter efficiency and power density. Although either the SSA approach or a signal flow graph may be used to get the differential equations, the SSA method was chosen in this research. The size of the ripple in the inductor current and capacitor voltage is governed by the gradient of the inductor current at each time interval as well as the length of the time interval. This is also true for the gradient of the capacitor voltage and the length of the time interval. In this study, the various mathematical formulas that are utilized to estimate the magnetizing inductance, capacitance, and inductance of various network components were investigated.

Ping-Ching *et al.* [288] provided a modified circuit design that takes into account the influence of the on-resistance of a MOSFET. To reduce inductor current, the time during which energy is given to the inductor is reduced to a minimal value. The phenomenon of zero voltage switching (ZVS) occurs when the switches are switched off [322]. Bae *et al.* [119] developed a soft-switched multiple-input buck-boost converter with a high power-conversion efficiency architecture. Their study delves into the operation of a two-input buck-boost converter. Although this circuit outperforms a traditional converter in terms of power conversion efficiency, it provides little insight into circuit parameter design. Chuan *et al.* [312] offered an enhanced version of the aforementioned topology that included a high frequency (HF) transformer. Utilizing logic gates, a two-switch buck-boost converter is given a two-edge modulation in order to lower the amount of inductor current ripple. This design is predicated on the supposition that the rectifier voltage's trailing edge has the potential to reduce the inductor current's ripple. When switching between no-load and full-load operation, the input voltage might cause the output voltage to become unstable due to the two-mode control system's design. To get a new working voltage range, a hysteresis voltage is introduced (buck-boost mode). The experimental findings indicate that the current ripple produced by the buck-boost topology is significantly less than that produced by other topologies. An integrated converter that consisted of buck and buck-boost converters that were coupled in parallel with a common inductor was the subject of research conducted by Mummadi [323]. Utilizing a common inductor provides users with a number of benefits. First, the results are generated in a second-order network, making it simple to analyse the dynamic behavior. Second, the converter's and magnetic core's size are lowered. Third, a minimal filter setup can be used to decrease ripple. Dynamic equations are subjected to state-space analysis.

Jintao *et al.* [324] introduced a converter design that enhances the efficiency of duty cycle consumption by including a decoupling capacitor into an H-bridge topology. This was done in order to improve duty cycle utilization. In addition, when compared to other topologies, this circuit possesses advantages such as reduced power loss and a lower overall cost than the alternatives. Kirciolu *et al.* [325] looked at buck, boost, and buck-boost converter topologies that were able to perform MPPT tracking with the use of a DSP-based MPPT controller. A proportional integral (PI) compensator is incorporated into this controller, in addition to discrete time control. MPPT strategies including the incremental conductance algorithm, the P&O algorithm, voltage feedback, and the direct technique are utilized in the tracking efficiency analysis process. Other strategies like the voltage feedback method also play a role. Because of this, as compared to other MPPT techniques, incremental conductance has a superior tracking efficiency under both slow and rapid changing conditions. When compared to the efficiency of buck converters that use other conversion techniques, the efficiency of buck converters that use these procedures is significantly higher.

4.3. SEPIC converter

SEPIC can alleviate the problems associated with buck-boost converters, such as pulsing load current and inverted load voltage [27], [40], [46], [50], [53], [56], [73], [121], [131], [141], [144], [193], [261]–[263], [274], [272], [275], [310], [311], [319], [326]–[343]. Buck-boost converters have a low efficiency when compared to SEPIC and Cuk converters [265]. Vuthchhay *et al.* [333], [336] suggested SEPIC models while operating in DCM and CCM. Three circuit states within one switching period were used to generate steady-state equations: 1) Although the MOSFET switch is activated, the diode is not conducting; 2) Although the MOSFET switch is switched off, the diode is conducting; and 3) Although the MOSFET switch is off, the diode is not conducting. The transfer function for feedback design is computed using the small-signal linear model developed for the aforementioned parameters. DCM operation improves dynamic responsiveness, reduces control complexity, and removes the reverse-recovery problem in diodes. The SEPIC operating in discontinuous capacitor voltage mode was explored for two circuit conditions during a switching time of T_s to produce the small-signal linear mode. In the first step, the MOSFET is turned on for DT_s intervals, and off for an interval of $(1-D)T_s$ in the second.

Because it is such an important consideration in converter design, Babaei *et al.* [334] looked at the ripple in the output voltage of a SEPIC while it was operating in CCM and DCM. The magnitude of the

maximum voltage ripple was measured and recorded for each of the base values of the input voltage and load resistance. When calculating the base values of the equivalent inductance and capacitance, the minimum values of the maximum output voltage ripple were utilized since they are the most stable. Complete-inductor supply mode (CISM) and incomplete-inductor supply mode are the two operating modes that may be used with CCM (IISM). Only the IISM DCM was looked at for this test. The output voltage ripple (OVR) waveforms that were produced for each operating mode were illustrated versus the corresponding inductance for values of frequency, capacitance, and load resistance that remained constant during the experiment. Additionally, the effect that inductances have on the efficiency of SEPIC was explored in this research.

A modified SEPIC with an additional diode and capacitor was presented by Bianchin *et al.* [329]. This SEPIC has less input current ripple and may function as a pre regulator because of its characteristics. The functioning of a DCM converter reduces commutation losses and ensures both high efficiency and the absence of ripple in the input current. In addition to analyzing the proposed device's properties as a converter and regulator, the study highlighted certain techniques to decrease input current distortion and constraints. These techniques include a low power factor and the requirement of an auxiliary in-rush limiter circuit for rectifier setup. The study also highlighted certain techniques to decrease input current distortion and constraints. During the design phase of the circuit, special attention should be paid to ensuring that it runs in DCM so that current ripple may be avoided. The most important need for this design is that at switching periods, each and every component of the circuit, including the voltage on the capacitor, must be deemed to be in excellent working order. A design that makes use of the resonant frequency was also shown to be effective. A predetermined resonance frequency value was chosen at random for the sake of this article, and the components were designed with that frequency value in mind. An open-loop control action with an analog implementation was used to analyze the change in total input current harmonic distortion, power factor, and efficiency across a variety of input voltage ranges. This was done in order to reduce the amount of third-harmonic distortion and maximize efficiency.

To perform steady-state and small-signal analysis on converter dynamic equations, harmonic balancing techniques, which apply Fourier analysis to dynamic equations of average and ripple values, can be utilized. These approaches use dynamic equations to represent average and ripple values. This approach is helpful in estimating the devices' ability to withstand switching stress for brief periods of time [337]. Through the utilization of soft switching technologies such as ZVS and zero current switching, input current ripple may be decreased (ZCS). When compared to hard-switched converters, the switching loss in the soft-switched PWM SEPIC developed by Kim *et al.* [310] is significantly lower. The peak-to-peak ripple current and voltage are taken into consideration when selecting the input inductor and capacitor; a ripple factor of 25% is used for this calculation. An inductor-current-control loop and an output-voltage-control loop are both present in this circuit. The inductor-current-control loop regulates the inductor current so that the reference voltage can be generated, and the output-voltage-control loop regulates the output voltage so that the command signal for the current controller can be generated. The challenge brought on by abrupt switching can be sidestepped with the use of a quasi-resonant SEPIC circuit that operates at a constant switching frequency. The fundamental conventional SEPIC circuit is modified in order to achieve ZVS switching over a broad input and output range. This is done by connecting capacitances in parallel with a MOSFET switch and a diode, and by connecting an inductor in series with a coupling capacitor. Both of these connections are made in the basic circuit.

Quamruzzaman *et al.* [344] proposed using the coupled-inductor SEPIC to achieve an array current with less ripple and enhanced dynamic responsiveness for PV sources. If there is a lot of ripples on the input side of the converter, the average value of the input current can be lower as a result. The detection of this lower average value may lead to inaccurate conclusions using the MPPT. To eliminate current ripple, a coupling coefficient of 0.97 is used to determine the values of inductors. P&O handles MPPT tracking in this article. According to the simulation findings, the linked SEPIC has an overall system efficiency of 97.01%. However, waves cannot be totally eliminated. Another issue is that voltage mismatch can generate ripple owing to non-zero DC parasitic capacitance of inductors. A circuit design described by Veerachary [332] can reduce ripple even more. This work explained how to approximate M in order to cancel the ripple in L_1 the L_2 . The SSA methodology was utilized in the development of the mathematical model depicting the working of the converter in CCM. The preceding modeling approach has a drawback in that it is predicated on the assumption that the entire system is linear. This is a significant limitation of the approach.

The combination of a linked inductor and an auxiliary inductor has several advantages, including smooth voltage switching and reduced ripple content. To mitigate SEPIC's high voltage stress, Hyun-Lark [272] created a modified voltage multiplier circuit. The magnetizing inductance equation, L_m , is derived from the ZVS condition as (9). The (10) gives the sum of the auxiliary and resonant inductances, L_a and L_r . The requirement that must be met during the design of the resonant capacitor to obtain the ZCS across the diode at the output side is shown in (11).

$$L_m < \frac{V_{in} D T_s}{2n \left(\frac{M}{\eta} + 1\right) I_o} \quad (9)$$

$$L_a + L_r = n(1 - n)L_m \quad (10)$$

$$d_{op} < 1 - D \quad (11)$$

where D represents the duty ratio, I_o represents the output current average, n represents the turns ratio of coupled inductor, M represents the gain of voltage, T_s represents the period of switching, V_{in} represents the input voltage, η represents the efficiency, and d_{op} represents the output-diode current-reset timing ratio.

Even though resonant capacitors and inductors are intended to cut down on switching loss, the values of the capacitors and inductors still need to be thoroughly investigated in order to ensure that all switches have smooth switching. Sheng *et al.* [342] showed that a multiple-input isolated SEPIC (MIISEPIC) might work in CCM when connected with an interleaved inductor. In order to construct a current-control loop for MPP control, the focus of this study was placed on the input current range's capabilities. The construction of a connected inductor that has a high magnetizing inductance to leakage inductance proportion and that can offer a wide controllable input-current range and good efficiency was the subject of this research. A unique triggering mechanism and zero-ripple technology were created in order to increase the effectiveness of the converter and lengthen its lifespan. Inductor current, capacitor voltage, and output voltage dynamic equations for MIISEPIC were obtained after doing research on the converter with two inputs. A variety of input switching sequences, switching frequencies, and magnetizing inductance value ranges were also studied in connection to possible input current ranges.

A circuit that generates a constant output current was reported by Al-Saffar *et al.* [338]. This circuit was created by adding a high-frequency transformer to a conventional SEPIC. An active clamp subcircuit is supplied, and its purpose is to reset the transformer. Despite the greater voltage stress across the primary power switch, this arrangement provides advantages such as continuous output current, less output voltage ripple, and lower switching current stress. In the course of CCM and DCM, this effort also analyzed the configuration of the system. A SEPIC equipped with peak input current mode control was developed by De Melo *et al.* [345]. While the input voltage regulating circuit is responsible for producing a current signal, MPPT and the battery-charging loop are responsible for producing a voltage signal. In order to compute the value of the input inductor, the peak-to-peak value of the input current is employed. When determining the value of the capacitor on the input side, the equivalent series resistance is what is employed for the calculation. In addition to that, the study outlined a transfer function approach to the process of creating a voltage controller. Incorporating current-mode control makes things more complicated, which makes things more complicated all around.

The level of ripple in the input current serves as the basis for calculating the value of the input inductance. The values of the series capacitance and multiplier capacitance may be determined by using the voltage ripple produced by a high-frequency capacitor. In order to calculate the output capacitance value of a low-frequency capacitor, the voltage ripple of the capacitor is employed. When the duty cycle value is getting closer to one, this circuit is able to achieve its maximum potential static gain. Magnetic coupling is the only method that permits an increase in static gain without requiring a corresponding change in the duty cycle [345]. Nur *et al.* [335] looked at how the properties of SEPIC were affected by the parasitic resistance of inductors. The MPPT calculation is carried out via the P&O algorithm. The voltage dips that are induced by the parasitic resistance are what make up the average voltage that is measured across the inductor. Both efficiency and ripple will be affected as a result of this. As the amount of parasitic resistance in the circuit grows, the converter's voltage gain, current gain, and output power all decrease. The findings of the simulation indicate that a greater amount of parasitic resistance can help reduce peak-to-peak current ripple.

4.4. Cuk converter

A negative capacitive output is characteristic of a Cuk converter, much like that of a buck-boost converter [28], [31], [116], [138], [147], [319], [326], [327], [341], [346]–[351]. The Cuk converter is unusual from other comparable devices in that it stores energy and transmits power using a capacitor rather than an inductor. This makes it possible for the Cuk converter to perform both functions simultaneously. The polarity of the input voltage is inverted in the Cuk converter, which results in the output voltage having the opposite sign. This particular converter, when properly connected, offers free ripple output, which may be useful for a wide range of applications [352]. Depending on the Cuk converters, several converter circuit topologies are introduced in [353]. The efficiency of the revised Cuk converter has substantially improved. This converter is renowned for its good bidirectional performance in managing current and voltage [116]. Furthermore, many forms of traditional Cuk converters have been published in the literature [147], [308], [326], [340], [352], the modified Cuk converter having a higher efficiency level for controlling voltage and current in bidirectional operation [319]. Sliding mode control (SMC) and proportional-integral control (PIC) are two strategies used in the closed-loop system concept (PI). It may also be used in conjunction with a fuzzy logic controller (FLC)

to calculate the output voltage of a Cuk converter [346], [353]. Furthermore, the Cuk converter may be used in brushless DC (BLDC) motor and renewable energy system applications such as PWM-based solar energy harvesting [351], [354]–[357].

The converter that is presented in [348] incorporates the switched-inductor and the switched-capacitor into the Cuk converter, which significantly enhances the voltage gain of the Cuk converter. This is done in order to improve the voltage gain of the Cuk converter. It is proposed in [286] that a high-gain boost-Cuk converter may be constructed by merging the quadratic boost converter and the Cuk converter; however, the output current of this converter is not continuous. A quadratic Cuk converter with an isolation transformer is proposed in [347]. This converter allows the voltage gain to be altered by changing the turns ratio of the transformer; however, this results in a relatively large amount of voltage stress on the switching device as well as input current ripple. Not only may magnetic integration of the inductors in interleaved converters lower the current ripple in the inductors, but it can also increase the converter's dynamic responsiveness [358], [359]. A two-phase transformer magnetic integrated equivalent circuit model was suggested in the aforementioned piece of literature [360], and it was then used to a two-phase interleaved forward converter.

Cuk and SEPIC converters are utilized as output terminals in [361] for combination converters to create a combined Cuk-SEPIC converter with a bipolar output and a longer converter life. Baptista *et al.* [350] employs parallel boost and Cuk to realize the converter's architecture, however the parallel capacitor on the output side causes the converter's output voltage to fluctuate. Li *et al.* [349] propose a unique boost-Cuk converter made up of basic boost and Cuk. By sharing the same input, a single switch boost-Cuk converter is presented. A boost-Cuk converter with a switching inductor is achieved by substituting the inductor with a switching inductor in order to increase voltage gain. The switching inductor's stray inductance is used to minimize the diode's reverse recovery. In addition, the converter's inductor is magnetically integrated to decrease the current ripple of the input and output inductors. Furthermore, the coupling magnetic integration technology reduces the input and output current ripple. As a result, this converter features a single switch, continuous input and output currents, and minimal ripple.

4.5. Zeta converter

A new soft switching converter that integrates the flyback and Zeta converters was studied by [40], [112], [144], [176], [212], [254], [294], [311], [316], [340], [362]–[364]. In the proposed converter, the flyback and Zeta topologies use the same power switches to reduce the power switch count. The output circuits in the flyback and Zeta converters are connected in parallel on the secondary side of the transformer to share the load current. The boost type of active clamp circuit is used to recycle the surge energy stored in the leakage inductance, limit the peak voltage stresses of all switches, and achieve the ZVS turn-on of all switches [67], [233], [308]. When the main switch is turned on, the power is transferred from the input voltage source to the output load through the Zeta converter. When the main switch is turned off and the auxiliary switch is turned on, the energy stored in the clamp capacitor and the magnetizing inductor is transferred to the output load through the flyback converter.

Two Zeta DC-DC converters are used for reducing the output voltage ripple. Two zeta converters are operated simultaneously for the purposes of reducing the output ripple, sharing the primary side components, and sharing the load current. The two converters are operated out of phase for this simultaneous operation [363]. A novel transformer less buck boost converter based on the Zeta converter is presented [365]. In this converter, only one main switch is used, which decreases the losses and improves efficiency. The active switch voltage stress is low and a switch with low on-state resistance can be utilized. The voltage gain of the converter is higher than that of the classic boost, buck-boost, Zeta, Cuk, and SEPIC converters. The presented converter structure is simple; hence, the converter control is simple.

A modified Zeta converter acts as an interface and is placed between the PV module and the load [254]. Equated with existing DC-DC converters, the modified Zeta converter comprises limiting of overload current ability as well as rapid parameter-based loading response. The modified-Zeta converter operates in discontinuous current mode with a high-power factor coefficient, reducing controller complexities and accurately regulating output voltage. Moreover, the modified Zeta converter has limitations over shading current behavior as well as rapid parameter response to the load as well as supply voltage situations.

A novel high step-up DC-DC converter is named the Integrated Quadratic-Boost-Zeta Converter [294]. It is based on the combination of two well-known DC-DC converter circuits: the Isolated Zeta converter and the Quadratic-Boost converter. The output voltage boosting is accomplished by summing both the output voltages of the Zeta and the QuadraticBoost. The circuit is designed in such a way that each part of the converter outputs keeps the same characteristics as its former converter, guaranteeing their well-known advantages. Furthermore, the proposed topology has a single-switch, maintaining a low component count. In addition, because of the high current ripple presented in the quadratic-boost converter, the proposed circuit, with an adequate filter design, can ensure a low output current ripple due to the Zeta output inductor.

4.6. Z-source converter

The Z-source comprises two identical inductors and two capacitors, in which the modernization of this configuration has been fluent and conducted to achieve better performance [87], [102], [122], [166], [291], [300], [314], [366]–[368]. A modified Z-source DC-DC converter is proposed by [367]. In comparison to the conventional Z-source dc-dc converter, the proposed converter can achieve higher voltage gain while putting less voltage stress on the switch and the impedance network capacitor and operating with a wider range of loads. Therefore, the proposed Z-source dc-dc converter not only has a lower cost but also has a smaller weight and size. In this paper [366], a modified double input DC-DC Z-Source for renewable energy PV/battery applications is presented. All of the operating modes are analyzed and then voltage gain is calculated for three states that show the proposed converter is very suitable for stand-alone applications. Also, due to the fewer number of switches, passive and active elements, the power loss is reduced and, because of the output voltage boosted by the modified Z-Source, it can satisfy high voltage requirements.

The suggested architecture takes advantage of the benefits offered by impedance-source converters in addition to those offered by cascaded converters. This is accomplished by contemplating the notion of cascading two Z-source networks within a typical boost converter. The suggested converter may deliver a large voltage gain by the application of specific changes, while maintaining a low voltage stress on the switch and the diodes at the same time. In addition, because the converter has such a low ripple in its input current, it is totally suitable for use in photovoltaic applications, which can lengthen the lifetime of PV panels. The high step-up DC-DC impedance source-based boost converter that has been suggested [291] consists of two cascaded Z-source networks as well as two switched-capacitor-inductor cells. A single ferrite core is used in the converter, and it has a total of six connected inductors that are included into the impedance network and the cells. Two of the most significant issues with this converter are the very high input current ripple and the high voltage stress that the switch experiences. Therefore, in order to make the converter actually usable, there will inevitably be certain modifications that need to be made. The significant input current ripple is still regarded a problem in this converter, despite the fact that the voltage stress of the switch may be clamped at a fixed value with the addition of a capacitor.

5. CONCLUSION

DC-DC converters are used extensively in solar energy harvesting systems because they enable more effective utilization of solar cells, which is the primary reason for their widespread use. The reason for this is that DC-DC converters allow for the more efficient exploitation of solar cells. However, one of the challenges is in selecting an appropriate converter, which is one of the obstacles because it has an effect on how the PV system operates. This is one of the reasons why this is such a difficult task. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the latest developments in DC-DC converter topologies, including boost, buck-boost, single-ended primary-inductance converter (SEPIC), Cuk, Zeta, and Z-source topologies. Comparisons of the topologies have been made in order to provide specific details on the difficulty of the hardware, the cost of implementation, the efficiency of the energy transfer elements, the efficiency of the tracking, and the efficiency of the converters. These comparisons were made so that specific details could be provided. This paper can be used as a quick guide to help you choose the best converter topology for projects that involve collecting energy from the sun.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is funded by a grant from the Institute of Research and Community Services (LPPM), Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, under contract number PUPS-297/SP3/LPPM-UAD/VI/2021. This study is also supported by the Embedded Systems and Power Electronics Research Group (ESPERG).

REFERENCES

- [1] P. A. Kumari and P. Geethanjali, "Parameter estimation for photovoltaic system under normal and partial shading conditions: A survey," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 84, no. September 2016, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.051.
- [2] A. Ramadan, S. Kamel, I. B. M. Taha, and M. Tostado-Véliz, "Parameter estimation of modified double-diode and triple-diode photovoltaic models based on wild horse optimizer," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 18, p. 2308, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3390/electronics10182308.
- [3] M. H. Ali, M. Mehanna, and E. Othman, "Optimal planning of RDGs in electrical distribution networks using hybrid SAPSO algorithm," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6153–6163, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp6153-6163.
- [4] W. Obaid, A.-K. Hamid, and C. Ghenai, "Hybrid solar/wind/diesel water pumping system in Dubai, United Arab Emirates," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 2062–2067, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i3.pp2062-2067.

- [5] W. Obaid, A.-K. Hamid, C. Ghenai, and M. El Haj Assad, "Design of a thermoelectric energy source for water pumping applications: A case study in Sharjah, United Arab Emirates," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 4751–4758, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i6.pp4751-4758.
- [6] M. Traore, A. Ndiaye, and S. Mbodji, "A comparative study of meta-heuristic and conventional optimization techniques of grid connected photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2492–2500, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2492-2500.
- [7] M. H. M. Ali, M. M. S. Mohamed, N. M. Ahmed, and M. B. A. Zahran, "Comparison between P&O and SSO techniques based MPPT algorithm for photovoltaic systems," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 32–40, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i1.pp32-40.
- [8] M. Ouremchi, S. El Mouzouade, K. El Khadiri, A. Tahiri, and H. Qjidaa, "Integrated energy management converter based on maximum power point tracking for photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1211–1222, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i2.pp1211-1222.
- [9] A. C. Subrata, T. Sutikno, Sunardi, A. Pamungkas, W. Arsadiando, and A. R. C. Baswara, "A laboratory scale IoT-based measuring of the solar photovoltaic parameters," *International Journal of Reconfigurable and Embedded Systems (IJRES)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 135–145, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijres.v11.i2.pp135-145.
- [10] M. Ehtesham and M. Junaid, "Reactive power control strategy for integrated photovoltaic inverter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1713–1720, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1713-1720.
- [11] T. Sutikno, A. C. Subrata, and M. H. Jopri, "Milestone of the most used maximum power point tracking in solar harvesting system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1277–1284, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1277-1284.
- [12] N. A. Windarko *et al.*, "Hybrid photovoltaic maximum power point tracking of Seagull optimizer and modified perturb and observe for complex partial shading," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4571–4585, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4571-4585.
- [13] A. K. Podder, N. K. Roy, and H. R. Pota, "MPPT methods for solar PV systems: a critical review based on tracking nature," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 1615–1632, 2019, doi: 10.1049/iet-rpg.2018.5946.
- [14] N. Hashim, N. F. N. Ismail, D. Johari, I. Musirin, and A. A. Rahman, "Optimal population size of particle swarm optimization for photovoltaic systems under partial shading condition," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4599–4613, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4599-4613.
- [15] A. Al-Gizi, A. H. Miry, and M. A. Shehab, "Optimization of fuzzy photovoltaic maximum power point tracking controller using chimp algorithm," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4549–4558, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4549-4558.
- [16] K. Kommuri and V. R. Kolluru, "Implementation of modular MPPT algorithm for energy harvesting embedded and IoT applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 3660, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i5.pp3660-3670.
- [17] S. H. Chong, N. N. Chandren, and C. R. Allan Soon, "Output energy maximization of a single axis photovoltaic solar tracking system: Experimental verification," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1655–1661, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1655-1661.
- [18] B. Hoxha, R. Selimaj, D. Krasniqi, and S. Osmanaj, "Cogeneration of energy in solar systems-a study case, Kosovo," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1675–1686, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1675-1686.
- [19] N.-E. Tariba, N. Ikken, A. Haddou, A. Bouknadel, H. El Omari, and H. El Omari, "Integral sliding-mode controller for maximum power point tracking in the grid-connected photovoltaic systems," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 4400–4415, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp4400-4415.
- [20] A. Benali, M. Khiat, and M. Denai, "Voltage profile and power quality improvement in photovoltaic farms integrated medium voltage grid using dynamic voltage restorer," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1481–1490, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.pp1481-1490.
- [21] S. Z. Islam, M. L. Othman, N. Mariun, H. Hizam, and N. Ayuni, "Feasibility analysis of standalone pv powered battery using SEN for smart grid," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 667–676, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp667-676.
- [22] M. Qawaqzeh, R. Zaitsev, O. Miroshnyk, M. Kirichenko, D. Danylchenko, and L. Zaitseva, "High-voltage DC converter for solar power station," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2135–2144, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp2135-2144.
- [23] H. Attia, "Artificial neural network based unity power factor corrector for single phase DC-DC converters," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 4145–4154, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp4145-4154.
- [24] S. A. H. Mohammed and I. M. Abdulbaqi, "Design and implementation of an impressed current cathodic protection system for buried metallic pipes (Part II) (considering Al-Quds gas station in Baghdad)," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 275–283, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp275-283.
- [25] A. Hassoune, M. Khafallah, A. Mesbahi, A. Nouaiti, and T. Bouragba, "Experimental implementation of a smart battery charger for electric vehicles charging station," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1689–1699, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp1689-1699.
- [26] M. A. Ibrahim, "Performance evaluation of pi controller for positive output Luo converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1816–1825, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp1816-1825.
- [27] M. Vaigundamoorthi, R. Ramesh, V. V. Prabhu, and K. A. Kumar, "MPPT oscillations minimization in PV system by controlling non-linear dynamics in SEPIC DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6268–6275, 2020, doi: 10.11591/IJECE.V10I6.PP6268-6275.
- [28] C. A. Ramos-Paja, D. González-Motoya, J. P. Villegas-Ceballos, S. I. Serna-Garcés, and R. Giral, "Sliding-mode controller for a photovoltaic system based on a Ćuk converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 2027–2044, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i3.pp2027-2044.
- [29] D. Ramya and D. Godwin Immanuel, "Implementation of non-isolated three-port converter through augmented time response," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 913–923, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp913-923.
- [30] A. A. M. Faudzi, S. F. Toha, R. A. Hanifah, N. F. Hasbullah, and N. A. Kamisan, "An interleaved dc charging solar system for electric vehicle," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2414–2422, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2414-2422.

- [31] S. S. Saswat, S. Patra, D. P. Mishra, S. R. Salkuti, and R. N. Senapati, "Harnessing wind and solar PV system to build hybrid power system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2160–2168, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2160-2168.
- [32] M. A. N. Amran, A. A. Bakar, M. H. A. Jalil, A. F. H. A. Gani, and E. Pathan, "Optimal tuning of proportional-integral controller using system identification for two-phase boost converter for low-voltage applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2393–2402, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2393-2402.
- [33] K. Zeb *et al.*, "Design of fuzzy-PI and fuzzy-sliding mode controllers for single-phase grid-connected transformerless photovoltaic inverter," *Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 520, May 2019, doi: 10.3390/electronics8050520.
- [34] L. Mitra and U. K. Rout, "Optimal control of a high gain DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 256–266, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i1.pp256-266.
- [35] K. Mohammad, M. Ahmad, S. A. Farooqui, W. Ali, and F. Khan, "Performance evaluation of a PMDC motor with battery storage control and MPPT based solar photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1704–1712, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1704-1712.
- [36] R. M. Jassim, K. H. Hassan, and I. A. Abed, "Comparison between boost and positive output super lift Luo converters to improve the performance of photovoltaic system," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2479–2490, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.3941.
- [37] K. Gaikwad, "Novel Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm for solar tree application," *2015 International Conference on Energy Systems and Applications*, 2015, pp. 189–193, doi: 10.1109/ICESA.2015.7503337.
- [38] M. Asna *et al.*, "Analysis and design of single phase voltage-frequency converter with optimized PI controller," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 522–529, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp522-529.
- [39] C. S. Purohit, M. Geetha, P. Sanjeevikumar, P. K. Maroti, S. Swami, and V. K. Ramachandramurthy, "Performance analysis of DC/DC bidirectional converter with sliding mode and pi controller," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 357–365, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp357-365.
- [40] S. Niranjana and B. Baskaran, "Performance evaluation of SEPIC, Luo and ZETA converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 374–380, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp374-380.
- [41] S. Miqoi, A. El Ougli, and B. Tidhaf, "Adaptive fuzzy sliding mode based MPPT controller for a photovoltaic water pumping system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 414–422, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp414-422.
- [42] H. A. Attia and F. Del Ama Gonzalo, "Stand-alone pv system with mppt function based on fuzzy logic control for remote building applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 842–851, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.pp842-851.
- [43] M. A. F. Al-Qaisi, M. A. Shehab, A. Al-Gizi, and M. Al-Saadi, "High performance DC/DC buck converter using sliding mode controller," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1806–1814, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.1806-1814.
- [44] T. Arunkumari and V. Indragandhi, "An overview of high voltage conversion ratio DC-DC converter configurations used in DC micro-grid architectures," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 77, pp. 670–687, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.04.036.
- [45] D. G and S. N. Singh, "Selection of non-isolated DC-DC converters for solar photovoltaic system," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 76, pp. 1230–1247, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.03.130.
- [46] R. A. Aprilianto, S. Subiyanto, and T. Sutikno, "Modified SEPIC Converter performance for grid-connected PV systems under various conditions," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 2943–2953, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.12928/telkomnika.v16i6.10148.
- [47] H. A. Hussein, H. J. Motlak, and H. N. A. Almusawi, "Effect of switched-capacitor on super-lift Luo converter," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 3119–3126, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i6.3604.
- [48] U. H. Salman, S. F. Nawaf, and M. O. Salih, "Studying and analyzing the performance of photovoltaic system by using fuzzy logic controller," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1687–1695, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i3.3680.
- [49] I. Alhamrouni, M. Salem, Y. Zahraoui, B. Ismail, A. Jusoh, and T. Sutikno, "Multi-input interleaved DC-DC converter for hybrid renewable energy applications," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1765–1778, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i3.3779.
- [50] B. N. Abramovich, D. A. Ustinov, and W. J. Abdallah, "Modified proportional integral controller for single ended primary inductance converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1007–1025, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1007-1025.
- [51] H. Attia and A. Elkhateb, "Intelligent maximum power point tracker enhanced by sliding mode control," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1037–1046, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1037-1046.
- [52] J. Gurram, N. S. Babu, and G. N. Srinivas, "Artificial neural network based DC-DC converter for grid connected transformerless PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1246–1254, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1246-1254.
- [53] D. S. Sankaralingam, M. S. B. Natarajan, M. Muthusamy, and S. B. Singh, "A novel metaheuristic approach for control of SEPIC converter in a standalone PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science, pp. 1082–1092, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1082-1092.
- [54] N. A. Shalash, W. R. Abdul-Adheem, and Y. K. A. Jabbar, "Control of shunt-wound motors with DC/DC converters using the pole placement technique," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 2335–2345, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i3.pp2335-2345.
- [55] R. K. Dasari and D. G. Immanuel, "Photovoltaic hybrid boost converter fed switched reluctance motor drive," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 275–288, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i1.pp275-288.
- [56] A. H. Mahmood, M. F. Mohammed, M. Omar, and A. H. Ahmad, "Single phase inverter fed through a regulated sepic converter," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 2921–2928, 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i6.2853.
- [57] F. T. Noori and T. K. Hassan, "Reactive power control of grid-connected photovoltaic microinverter based on third-harmonic injection," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2169–2181, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2169-2181.
- [58] E. J. Yun and C. G. Yu, "A self-startup DC-DC boost converter for thermal energy harvesting in a 0.35 μm CMOS process," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 3157–3165, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i6.4133.
- [59] I. A. Abed and S. H. Majeed, "Dc/dc converter control using suggested artificial intelligent controllers," *IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence (IJ-AI)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 847–857, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijai.v10.i4.pp847-857.

- [60] S. W. Shneen, D. H. Shaker, and F. N. Abdullah, "Simulation model of PID for DC-DC converter by using MATLAB," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 3791–3797, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i5.pp3791-3797.
- [61] A. Alizadeh Asl and R. Alizadeh Asl, "Modeling and control of a hybrid DC/DC/AC converter to transfer power under different power management strategies," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1620–1631, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i3.pp1620-1631.
- [62] I. K. Abdul-Razzaq, M. M. Fahim Sakr, and Y. G. Rashid, "Comparison of PV panels MPPT techniques applied to solar water pumping system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1813–1822, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i3.pp1813-1822.
- [63] Y. Boujoudar, M. Azeroual, H. Elmoussaoui, and T. Lamhamdi, "Intelligent control of battery energy storage for microgrid energy management using ANN," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2760–2767, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i4.pp2760-2767.
- [64] H. Azoug, H. Belmili, and F. Bouazza, "Grid-connected control of pv-wind hybrid energy system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1228–1238, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1228-1238.
- [65] G. B. Arjun Kumar, Shivashankar, and Keshavamurthy, "Design and control of grid-connected solar-wind integrated conversion system with dfig supplying three-phase four-wire loads," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1150–1161, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1150-1161.
- [66] N. Khaldi, Y. Barradi, K. Zazi, and M. Zazi, "Controller design for pv experimental bench with adrc strategy supervised by labview created interface," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1162–1176, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1162-1176.
- [67] S. Adarsh and H. Nagendrappa, "Duty ratio control of three port isolated bidirectional asymmetrical triple active bridge DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 943–956, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp943-956.
- [68] A. A. Chlaihawi, A. M. Al-Modaffer, and H. Jedi, "Minimal switching of multiple input multilevel output dc-dc converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 968–974, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp968-974.
- [69] A. A. Alzubaidi, L. A. Khaliq, H. S. Hamad, W. K. Al-Azzawi, M. S. Jabbar, and T. A. Shihab, "MPPT implementation and simulation using developed P&O algorithm for photovoltaic system concerning efficiency," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2460–2470, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.3949.
- [70] S. Zouga, M. Benchagra, and A. Ailane, "A robust nonlinear control strategy of a pv system connected to the three-phase grid based on backstepping and pso technique," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 612–626, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i1.pp612-626.
- [71] K. L. Shenoy, C. G. Nayak, and R. P. Mandi, "Effect of partial shading in grid connected solar pv system with fl controller," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 431–440, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i1.pp431-440.
- [72] D. Chowdhury, M. S. Miah, M. F. Hossain, and U. Sarker, "Implementation of a grid-tied emergency back-up power supply for medium and low power applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6233–6243, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp6233-6243.
- [73] B. Rajapandian and G. T. Sundarajan, "Evaluation of DC-DC converter using renewable energy sources," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1918–1925, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp1918-1925.
- [74] B. A. Numan, A. M. Shakir, and A. L. Mahmood, "Photovoltaic array maximum power point tracking via modified perturbation and observation algorithm," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2007–2018, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp2007-2018.
- [75] H. J. Motlak and A. S. Rahi, "Performance comparison of different control strategies for the regulation of DC-DC negative output super-lift Luo-converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 5785–5792, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp5785-5792.
- [76] M. Madark, A. Ba-Razzouk, E. Abdelmounim, and M. El Malah, "Linear and nonlinear controllers of a solar photovoltaic water pumping system," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1861–1872, 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i5.1778.
- [77] M. Nagaiah and K. C. Sekhar, "Analysis of fuzzy logic controller based bi-directional DC-DC converter for battery energy management in hybrid solar/wind micro grid system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2271–2284, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2271-2284.
- [78] D. S. Nayak and R. Shivarudraswamy, "Solar fed BLDC motor drive for mixer grinder using a boost converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 56–63, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp56-63.
- [79] T. Toumi, A. Allali, O. Abdelkhalek, A. B. Abdelkader, A. Meftouhi, and M. A. Soumeur, "PV integrated single-phase dynamic voltage restorer for sag voltage, voltage fluctuations and harmonics compensation," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 545–554, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp547-554.
- [80] E. N. Sholikhah, N. A. Windarko, and B. Sumantri, "Tunicate swarm algorithm based maximum power point tracking for photovoltaic system under non-uniform irradiation," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4559–4570, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4559-4570.
- [81] D. S. Nayak and R. Shivarudraswamy, "Solar fed BLDC motor drive for mixer grinder using a buck-boost converter," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 48–56, 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i1.1667.
- [82] Z. A. Ghani *et al.*, "Peripheral interface controller-based maximum power point tracking algorithm for photovoltaic DC to DC boost controller," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 240–250, 2020, doi: 10.12928/telkomnika.v18i1.12730.
- [83] S. Slamet, E. Rijanto, A. Nugroho, and R. A. Ghani, "A robust maximum power point tracking control for PV panel using adaptive PI controller based on fuzzy logic," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 2999–3009, 2020, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v18i6.17271.
- [84] R. Pazhanimurugan, R. Bensraj, and C. R. Balamurugan, "Time response of fopid controlled PV based cascaded landsman converter-inverter fed induction motor and electric drives applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1379–1387, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.pp1379-1387.
- [85] K. H. Chalok, M. F. N. Tajuddin, T. S. Babu, S. M. Ayob, and T. Sutikno, "Optimal extraction of photovoltaic energy using fuzzy logic control for maximum power point tracking technique," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science, pp. 1628–1639, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.1628-

- 1639.
- [86] R. H. G. Tan, C. B. Chuin, and S. G. Solanki, "Modeling of single phase off-grid inverter for small standalone system applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1398–1405, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.pp1398-1405.
- [87] M. Ado, A. Jusoh, T. Sutikno, M. H. Muda, and Z. A. Arfeen, "Dual output DC-DC quasi impedance source converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3988–3998, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp3988-3998.
- [88] S. Nagaraj, R. Ranihemamalini, and L. Rajaji, "Performance enhancement of DC/DC converters for solar powered EV," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3423–3430, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp3423-3430.
- [89] B. Hamlili, K. Benahmed, and B. Gasbaoui, "Behaviour of solar wireless sensor network in saharan region under different scenarios consideration," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2797–2806, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2797-2806.
- [90] T. Abderrahim, T. Abdelwahed, and M. Radouane, "Improved strategy of an MPPT based on the sliding mode control for a PV system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 3074–3085, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp3074-3085.
- [91] S. Supanyapong, W. Pattarapongsathit, A. Bilsalam, D. Guilbert, and P. Thounthong, "Averaged large-signal model of a DC-DC isolated forward resonant reset converter for a solar cell battery charger using internet of things: implementation," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1732–1747, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1732-1748.
- [92] D. S. Nayak and R. Shivarudraswamy, "A solar fed BLDC motor drive for mixer grinder using a buck converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1113–1121, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp1113-1121.
- [93] M. Moutchou and A. Jbari, "Fast photovoltaic IncCond-MPPT and backstepping control, using DC-DC boost converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1101–1112, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i1.pp1101-1112.
- [94] G. Sureshkumar, N. Kannan, and S. Thomas, "MATLAB/SIMULINK based simulations of KY converter for PV panels powered LED lighting system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1885–1893, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.1885-1893.
- [95] S. Della Krachai, A. Boudghene Stambouli, M. Della Krachai, and M. Bekhti, "Experimental investigation of artificial intelligence applied in MPPT techniques," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2138–2147, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2138-2147.
- [96] O. Lagdani, M. Trihi, and B. Bossoufi, "PV array connected to the grid with the implementation of MPPT algorithms (INC, P&O and FL method)," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2084–2095, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2084-2095.
- [97] W. Abitha Memala, C. Bhuvaneswari, S. M. Shyni, G. Merlin Sheeba, M. S. Mahendra, and V. Jaishree, "DC-DC converter based power management for go green applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2046–2054, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2046-2054.
- [98] A. M. Elsherbiny, A. S. Nada, and M. Kamal, "Smooth transition from grid to standalone solar diesel mode hybrid generation system with a battery," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2065–2075, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2065-2075.
- [99] M. Darameičikas *et al.*, "Improved design of a DC-DC converter in residential solar photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1476–1482, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1476-1482.
- [100] P. Sathyanarayana, R. Ballal, G. Kumar, and S. Shaileshwari, "Maximum power point optimization for a grid synchronized pv system considering partial shaded condition using multi-objective function," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1547–1554, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1547-1554.
- [101] S. Jayaprakash, R. Ramani, M. Kavitha, and V. S. Nayagam, "Comparison of solar based closed loop DC-DC converter using PID and ANN control for shunt motor drive," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1324–1328, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1324-1328.
- [102] R. G. Kumari, A. Ezhilarasi, and N. Pasula, "Control strategy for modified CI-based Bi-directional Γ -Z source DC-DC converter for buck-boost operation," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1510–1518, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1510-1518.
- [103] M. Z. Zulkifli, M. Azri, A. Alias, N. Talib, and J. M. Lazi, "Simple control scheme buck-boost DC-DC converter for stand alone PV application system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1090–1101, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.1090-1101.
- [104] A. Ibrahim, R. Aboelsaud, and S. Obukhov, "Maximum power point tracking of partially shading PV system using cuckoo search algorithm," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1081–1089, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.pp1081-1089.
- [105] K. Dhineshkumar, C. Subramani, A. Geetha, and C. Vimala, "Performance analysis of PV powered multilevel inverter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 753–760, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i2.pp.753-760.
- [106] M. Slimi, A. Boucheta, and B. Bouchiba, "Maximum power control for photovoltaic system using intelligent strategies," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 423–432, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp423-432.
- [107] M. H. A. Malek, F. Mustafa, and A. M. M. Asry, "A battery-less power supply using supercapacitor as energy storage powered by solar," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 568–574, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp568-574.
- [108] O. E. Maguiri, D. Moussaif, E. A. Smma, F. Abdelmajid, and A. Akhiate, "Backstepping nonlinear control to maximize energy capture in a variable speed wind turbine," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4758–4766, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i6.pp4758-4766.
- [109] M. El malah, A. Ba-Razzouk, M. Guisser, E. Abdelmounim, and M. Madark, "Backstepping based power control of a three-phase single-stage grid-connected PV system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4738–4748, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i6.pp4738-4748.

- [110] M. W. Umar, N. Yahaya, and Z. Baharudin, "State-space averaged modeling and transfer function derivation of DC-DC boost converter for high-brightness led lighting applications," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 1006–1013, 2019, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.V17I2.10272.
- [111] S. Ramamurthi and P. Ramasamy, "High step-up DC-DC converter with switched capacitor-coupled inductor and voltage multiplier module," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1599–1604, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1599-1604.
- [112] S. Semeskandeh, M. Hojjat, and M. H. Abardeh, "Design of a photovoltaic MPPT charge controller using DC-DC ZETA converter with a modified three-stage charging method," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1887–1894, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1887-1894.
- [113] D. C. Sekhar, P. V. V. R. Rao, and R. Kiranmayi, "A novel efficient adaptive-neuro fuzzy interfaced system control based smart grid to enhance power quality," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 3375–3387, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp3375-3387.
- [114] G. K. Kumar and D. Elangovan, "Review on fault-diagnosis and fault-tolerance for DC-DC converters," *IJET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2019.0672.
- [115] N. H. Baharudin, T. M. N. T. Mansur, F. A. Hamid, R. Ali, and M. I. Misrun, "Topologies of DC-DC converter in solar PV applications," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 368–374, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v8.i2.pp368-374.
- [116] N. Priyadarshi *et al.*, "Performance evaluation of solar-PV-based non-isolated switched-inductor and switched-capacitor high-step-up Cuk converter," *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 11, no. 9, p. 1381, 2022, doi: 10.3390/electronics11091381.
- [117] M. A. Farahat, H. M. B. Metwally, and A. Abd-Elfatah Mohamed, "Optimal choice and design of different topologies of DC-DC converter used in PV systems, at different climatic conditions in Egypt," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 43, pp. 393–402, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2011.10.021.
- [118] N. H. Baharudin, T. M. N. T. Mansur, F. A. Hamid, R. Ali, and M. I. Misrun, "Topologies of DC-DC converter in solar PV applications," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 368–374, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v8.i2.pp368-374.
- [119] S. Bae and J.-J. Yun, "High efficient multiple-input buck-boost converter for energy harvesting systems," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, 2016, pp. 577–578, doi: 10.1109/ICCE.2016.7430737.
- [120] M. Lu, G. Fu, N. B. Osman, and U. Konbr, "Green energy harvesting strategies on edge-based urban computing in sustainable internet of things," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 75, p. 103349, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2021.103349.
- [121] D. Ganesh, S. Moorthi, and H. Sudheer, "A voltage controller in photo-voltaic system with battery storage for stand-alone applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 9–18, 2012, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v2i1.127.
- [122] M. B. Kalashani and M. Farsadi, "New structure for photovoltaic system applications with maximum power point tracking ability," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 489–498, 2014, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v4i4.6365.
- [123] S. Das, P. K. Sadhu, N. Pal, G. Majumdar, and S. Mukherjee, "Solar photovoltaic powered sailing boat using buck converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 129–136, 2015, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v6.i1.pp129-136.
- [124] R. Balamurugan and R. Nithya, "FC/PV fed SAF with fuzzy logic control for power quality enhancement," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 470–476, 2015, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v5.i4.pp470-476.
- [125] L. H. Pratomo, F. D. Wijaya, and E. Firmansyah, "Impedance matching method in two-stage converters for single phase PV-grid system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 626–635, 2015, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v5i4.pp626-635.
- [126] P. Amaral, C. Duarte, and P. Costa, "On the impact of timer resolution in the efficiency optimization of synchronous buck converters," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 693–702, 2015, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v6.i4.pp693-702.
- [127] R. S. Ravi Sankar, S. V. Jaya Kumar, and K. K. Deepika, "Model predictive current control of grid connected PV systems," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 285–296, 2016, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v2.i2.pp285-296.
- [128] M. M. Ismail, "Daily constant PV output power supplying AC pumps using batteries," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 275–284, 2016, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v2.i2.pp275-284.
- [129] Y. Yang, "Direct instantaneous power control for three-level grid-connected inverters," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1260–1273, 2016, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v6i3.8193.
- [130] K. Muthukumar and T. S. Anandhi, "Real time implementation of variable step size based P&O MPPT for PV systems based on dSPACE," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 915–925, 2016, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v7.i3.pp915-925.
- [131] M. Oudda and A. Hazzab, "Photovoltaic system with SEPIC converter controlled by the fuzzy logic," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1283–1293, 2016, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v7i4.pp1283-1293.
- [132] A. A. Bakar, M. U. Wahyu, A. Ponniran, and T. Taufik, "Simulation and analysis of multiphase boost converter with soft-switching for renewable energy application," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1894–1902, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v8i4.pp1894-1902.
- [133] S. Jaisudha, S. Srinivasan, and G. Kanimozhi, "Bidirectional resonant DC-DC converter for microgrid application," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1548–1561, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v8i4.pp1548-1561.
- [134] Z. H. Ali, A. K. Ahmed, and A. T. Saeed, "Modeling solar modules performance under temperature and solar radiation of Western Iraq," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1842–1850, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n4.pp1842-1850.
- [135] W. I. Hameed, B. A. Sawadi, and A. M. Fadhil, "Voltage tracking control of DC-DC boost converter using fuzzy neural network," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1657–1665, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n4.pp1657-1665.
- [136] G. G. Raja Sekhar and B. Banakara, "An internal current controlled BLDC motor drive supplied with PV fed high voltage gain DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 2, Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science, pp. 1275–1285, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i2.pp1275-1285.

- [137] G. G. R. Sekliar and B. Baiiakara, "An internal current controlled BLDC motor drive supplied with PY Fed High voltage gain DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1262–1272, 2018, doi: 10.11591/IJECE.V8I2.PP1262-1272.
- [138] V. Vasudevan and K. Balaji, "Performance of Cuk-KY converter fed multilevel inverter for hybrid sources," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 436–445, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v10.i2.pp436-445.
- [139] M. Kavitha and V. Sivachidambaranathan, "Comparison of different control techniques for interleaved DC-DC converter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 641–647, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n2.pp641-647.
- [140] P. Sivagami and N. M. Jothi Swaroopan, "Performance measures of positive output superlift luo converter using multitudinous controller," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, pp. 704–711, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n2.pp704-711.
- [141] K. V. K. Varma and A. Ramkumar, "Novel M-SEPIC DC-DC converter for BLDC pumping system with active PFC using ANFIS controller," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 386–399, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v11.i1.pp386-399.
- [142] H. Attia, "Fuzzy logic controller effectiveness evaluation through comparative memberships for photovoltaic maximum power point tracking function," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1147–1156, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9n3.pp1147-1156.
- [143] G. G. Raja Sekhar and B. Banakar, "Solar PV fed non-isolated DC-DC converter for BLDC motor drive with speed control," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 313–323, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v13.i1.pp313-323.
- [144] S. Mondal and M. Chattopadhyay, "Comparative study of three different bridge-less converters for reduction of harmonic distortion in brushless DC motor," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1185–1193, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i3.pp1185-1193.
- [145] A. H. Mary, A. H. Miry, and M. H. Miry, "System uncertainties estimation based adaptive robust backstepping control for DC DC buck converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 1., pp. 347–355, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i1.pp347-355.
- [146] D. P. Mishra, R. Senapati, and S. R. Salkuti, "Comparison of DC-DC converters for solar power conversion system," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 648–655, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v26.i2.pp648-655.
- [147] A. F. Moghaddam and A. Van den Bossche, "A cuk converter cell balancing technique by using coupled inductors for lithium-based batteries," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 15, p. 2881, 2019, doi: 10.3390/en12152881.
- [148] A. Tomaszuk and A. Krupa, "High efficiency high step-up DC/DC converters - A review," *Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences: Technical Sciences*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 475–483, 2011, doi: 10.2478/v10175-011-0059-1.
- [149] Y. Mahmoud, W. Xiao, and H. H. Zeineldin, "A simple approach to modeling and simulation of photovoltaic modules," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 185–186, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2011.2170776.
- [150] R. R. Gopi and S. Sreejith, "Converter topologies in photovoltaic applications—A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 94, pp. 1–14, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2018.05.047.
- [151] F. Ding, P. Li, B. Huang, F. Gao, C. Ding, and C. Wang, "Modeling and simulation of grid-connected hybrid photovoltaic/battery distributed generation system," *CICED 2010 Proceedings*, 2010, pp. 1–10.
- [152] A. Chouder, S. Silvestre, N. Sadaoui, and L. Rahmani, "Modeling and simulation of a grid connected PV system based on the evaluation of main PV module parameters," *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 46–58, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.simpat.2011.08.011.
- [153] S. Said, A. Massoud, M. Benammar, and S. Ahmed, "A Matlab/Simulink-based photovoltaic array model employing SimPowerSystems toolbox," *Journal of Energy and Power Engineering* 6, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 1965–1975, 2012.
- [154] H. Tian, F. Mancilla-David, K. Ellis, E. Muljadi, and P. Jenkins, "A cell-to-module-to-array detailed model for photovoltaic panels," *Solar Energy*, vol. 86, no. 9, pp. 2695–2706, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2012.06.004.
- [155] K. Y. Khouzam, "Optimum load matching in direct-coupled photovoltaic power systems-application to resistive loads," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 265–271, June 1990, doi: 10.1109/60.107220.
- [156] V. Sumathi, R. Jayapragash, A. Bakshi, and P. K. Akella, "Solar tracking methods to maximize PV system output—A review of the methods adopted in recent decade," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 74, pp. 130–138, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.02.013.
- [157] H. Mousazadeh, A. Keyhani, A. Javadi, H. Mobli, K. Abrinia, and A. Sharifi, "A review of principle and sun-tracking methods for maximizing solar systems output," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 1800–1818, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2009.01.022.
- [158] T. Khan, M. Asim, M. S. Manzar, M. Ibrahim, and S. S. A. Ahmed, "Least mean sixth control approach for three-phase three-wire grid-integrated pv system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2131–2139, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2131-2139.
- [159] T. N. Manjunath, S. Mallikarjunaswamy, M. Komala, N. Sharmila, and K. S. Manu, "An efficient hybrid reconfigurable wind gas turbine power management system using mppt algorithm," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2501–2510, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2501-2510.
- [160] T. N. A. Nguyen, D. C. Pham, L. H. Minh, and N. H. C. Thanh, "Combined RBFN based MPPT and d-axis stator current control for permanent magnet synchronous generators," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2459–2469, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2459-2469.
- [161] A. Balal, M. Abedi, and F. Shahabi, "Optimized generated power of a solar pv system using an intelligent tracking technique," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2580–2592, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2580-2592.
- [162] H. Attia and S. Ulusoy, "A new perturb and observe MPPT algorithm based on two steps variable voltage control," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2201–2208, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2201-2208.
- [163] B. J. Abdulelah, Y. I. M. Al-Mashhadany, S. Alghuri, and G. Ulutagay, "Modeling and analysis: Power injection model approach for high performance of electrical distribution networks," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 2943–2952, 2021, doi: 10.11591/eei.v10i6.3126.
- [164] S. B. Utomo, I. Setiawan, B. Fajar, S. H. Winoto, and A. Marwanto, "Optimizing of the installed capacity of hybrid renewable energy with a modified MPPT model," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 73–81, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i1.pp73-81.

- [165] B. Sirisha and M. A. Nazeemuddin, "A novel five-level voltage source inverter interconnected to grid with srf controller for voltage synchronization," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 50–58, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i1.3274.
- [166] E. Najafi, A. H. Rashidi, and S. M. Dehghan, "Z-source reversing voltage multilevel inverter for photovoltaic applications with inherent voltage balancing," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 267–274, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i1.pp267-274.
- [167] Z. M. Abed, T. K. Hassan, and K. R. Hameed, "Analysis and design of photovoltaic three-phase grid-connected inverter using passivity-based control," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 167–177, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i1.pp167-177.
- [168] M. Nivas, R. K. P. R. Naidu, D. P. Mishra, and S. R. Salkuti, "Modeling and analysis of solar-powered electric vehicles," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 480–487, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i1.pp480-487.
- [169] H. Abbes, H. Abid, K. Loukil, M. Abid, and A. Toumi, "Fuzzy-based MPPT algorithm implementation on FPGA chip for multi-channel photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Reconfigurable and Embedded Systems (IJRES)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 49–58, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijres.v11.i1.pp49-58.
- [170] I. A. Smadi and A. Al-Ramaden, "An algorithm to extract the maximum power from the PV-based generation systems under non-uniform weather," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1129–1139, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1129-1139.
- [171] Y. Majdoub, A. Abbou, and M. Akherraz, "High-performance MPPT control of DFIG with optimized flux reference in presence of nonlinear magnetic characteristic," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 1195–1208, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i2.pp1195-1208.
- [172] B. Belkacem, N. Bouhamri, L. A. Koridak, and A. Allali, "Fuzzy optimization strategy of the maximum power point tracking for a variable wind speed system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 4264–4275, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp4264-4275.
- [173] A. Hilali, Y. Mardoude, Y. B. Akka, H. E. Alami, and A. Rahali, "Design, modeling and simulation of perturb and observe maximum power point tracking for a photovoltaic water pumping system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 3430–3439, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i4.pp3430-3439.
- [174] Y. E. A. Idrissi, K. Assalaou, L. Elmahni, and E. Aitiaz, "New improved MPPT based on artificial neural network and PI controller for photovoltaic applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1791–1801, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1791-1801.
- [175] H. Albalawi, S. A. Zaid, Y. M. Buswig, H. W. El-Rab, A. Lakhouti, and M. A. Arshad, "Wind energy management of a standalone system operating at maximum power point," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1884–1895, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1884-1895.
- [176] M. Hasan, W. H. Alhazmi, W. Zakri, and A. U. Khan, "Parameter estimation and control design of solar maximum power point tracking," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4586–4598, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4586-4598.
- [177] R. Kerid and Y. Bounnah, "Modeling and parameter estimation of solar photovoltaic based MPPT control using EKF to maximize efficiency," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2491–2499, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.3782.
- [178] N. Mezzai, S. Belaid, D. Rekioua, and T. Rekioua, "Optimization, design and control of a photovoltaic/wind turbine/battery system in Mediterranean climate conditions," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2938–3948, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.3872.
- [179] R. M. Abusharia and K. M. Al-Aubidy, "Embedded control unit design for energy management in smart homes," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2537–2546, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.4103.
- [180] A. Mansouri and F. Krim, "Optimized servo-speed control of wind turbine coupled to doubly fed induction generator," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 4688–4699, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i5.pp4688-4699.
- [181] M. F. Alvianandy, N. A. Windarko, and B. Sumantri, "Maximum power point tracking based on improved spotted hyena optimizer for solar photovoltaic," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 5775–5788, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i6.pp5775-5788.
- [182] M. Bahri, M. Talea, H. Bahri, and M. Aboufatah, "An efficient scanning algorithm for photovoltaic systems under partial shading," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 5799–5807, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i6.pp5799-5807.
- [183] M. Venugopal and G. V. Jayaramaiah, "Simulation and performance analysis of self-powered piezoelectric energy harvesting system for low power applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 5861–5871, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i6.pp5861-5871.
- [184] E. J. Yun, J. T. Park, and C. G. Yu, "An maximum power point tracking interface circuit for low-voltage DC-type energy harvesting sources," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 3108–3118, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i6.4124.
- [185] B. Subudhi and R. Pradhan, "A comparative study on maximum power point tracking techniques for photovoltaic power systems," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 89–98, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2012.2202294.
- [186] S. Sahbani, H. Mahmoudi, A. Hasnaoui, M. Kchikach, and H. Benchraa, "A novel fast MPPT strategy used for grid-connected residential PV system applied in Morocco," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 942–952, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp942-952.
- [187] S. Kamalakkannan and D. Kirubakaran, "Solar energy based impedance-source inverter for grid system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 102–108, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i1.pp102-109.
- [188] A. Yahya, H. El Fadil, and M. Oulcaid, "Output feedback nonlinear control of three-phase grid-connected PV generator," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 137–150, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp137-150.
- [189] S. Panigrahi and A. Thakur, "Modeling and simulation of three phases cascaded H-bridge grid-tied PV inverter," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2019, doi: 10.11591/eei.v8i1.1225.
- [190] M. I. Abuashour, T. O. Sweidan, M. S. Widyana, M. M. Hattab, and M. A. Ma'itah, "Operational performance of a PV generator feeding DC shunt and induction motors with MPPT," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 771–782, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i2.pp.771-782.
- [191] A. P. Yoganandini and G. S. Anitha, "A cost effective computational design of maximum power point tracking for photo-voltaic cell," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 851–860, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i2.pp.851-860.

- [192] M. Bouderbala, B. Bossoufi, A. Lagrioui, M. Taoussi, H. A. Aroussi, and Y. Ihedrane, "Direct and indirect vector control of a doubly fed induction generator based in a wind energy conversion system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1531–1540, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i3.pp1531-1540.
- [193] W. Margaret Amutha, H. Caleb Andrew, A. Debie Shajie, and J. Praveen, "Renewable power interface based rural telecom," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 917–927, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.917-927.
- [194] Himani and N. Sharma, "Hardware-in-the-loop simulator of wind turbine emulator using labview," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 971–986, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.971-986.
- [195] S. Mensou, A. Essadki, I. Minka, T. Nasser, B. B. Idrissi, and L. B. Tarla, "Performance of a vector control for dfig driven by wind turbine: Real time simulation using DS1104 controller board," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1003–1013, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.1003-1013.
- [196] Shashibhushan and S. Sonoli, "Starting torque and torque ripple reduction using svpwm based vector control of induction motor with nine-level cascaded multilevel inverter fed with solar PV power," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1123–1132, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i2.1123-1132.
- [197] M. N. Syah and Subiyanto, "Performance enhancement of maximum power point tracking for grid-connected photovoltaic system under various gradient of irradiance changes," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1973–1984, 2019, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v17i4.10335.
- [198] H. A. Attia, "High performance PV system based on artificial neural network MPPT with PI controller for direct current water pump applications," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems*, vol. 10, no. 3. Institute of Advanced Engineering and Science, pp. 1329–1338, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1329-1338.
- [199] F. Saadaoui, K. Mammam, and A. Hazzab, "Modeling of photovoltaic system with maximum power point tracking control by neural networks," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1575–1591, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1575-1591.
- [200] K. Saidi, M. Maamoun, and M. Bounekhla, "A new high performance variable step size perturb-and-observe MPPT algorithm for photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 1662–1674, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.1662-1674.
- [201] I. El Karaoui, M. Maaroufi, and B. Bossoufi, "Robust power control methods for wind turbines using -generator," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2101–2117, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2101-2117.
- [202] H. Otmane, M. Youssef, and B. Mokhtar, "Comparative analysis of cascaded fuzzy-PI controllers based-mppt and perturb and observe mppt in a grid-connected PV system operating under different weather and loading conditions," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1986–1994, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.1986-1994.
- [203] M. Yuhendri, M. Muskhir, and Taali, "A novel optimum tip speed ratio control of low speed wind turbine generator based on type-2 fuzzy system," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1189–1197, 2019, doi: 10.11591/eei.v8i4.1450.
- [204] Y. Baala and S. Bri, "Torque estimator using MPPT method for wind turbines," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1208–1219, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp1208-1219.
- [205] I. Yadav, S. K. Maurya, and G. K. Gupta, "A literature review on industrially accepted MPPT techniques for solar PV system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 2117–2127, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp2117-2127.
- [206] M. S. Ibbini and A. H. Adawi, "A SIMSCAPE based design of a dual maximum power point tracker of a stand-alone photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2912–2917, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2912-2917.
- [207] M. Makhad, M. Zazi, and A. Loulijat, "Nonlinear control of WECS based on PMSG for optimal power extraction," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 2815–2823, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i3.pp2815-2823.
- [208] Q.-V. Ngo, C. Yi, and T.-T. Nguyen, "The maximum power point tracking based-control system for small-scale wind turbine using fuzzy logic," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3927–3935, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i4.pp3927-3935.
- [209] A. Yasmine, B. Rafik, B. Rachid, and M. Adel, "Grid connected photovoltaic system efficiency and quality improvement using fuzzy-incond MPPT," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i3.pp1536-1546.
- [210] A. Haddou, N.-E. Tariba, N. Ikken, A. Bouknadel, H. E. L. Omari, and H. E. L. Omari, "Comparative study of new MPPT control approaches for a photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 251–262, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp251-262.
- [211] H. Hichem, M. Abdellah, T. A. Abderrazak, B. Abdelkader, and S. Ramzi, "A wind turbine sensorless automatic control systems, analysis, modelling and development of IDA-PBC method," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 45–55, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp45-55.
- [212] T. Winarno, L. N. Palupi, A. Pracoyo, and L. Ardhenta, "MPPT control of PV array based on PSO and adaptive controller," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 1113–1121, 2020, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v18i2.14845.
- [213] O. Zebraoui and M. Bouzi, "Improved MPPT controls for a standalone PV/wind/battery hybrid energy system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 988–1001, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp988-1001.
- [214] A. A. Firdaus, R. T. Yunardi, E. I. Agustin, S. D. N. Nahdliyah, and T. A. Nugroho, "An improved control for MPPT based on FL-PSO to minimize oscillation in photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1082–1087, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp1082-1087.
- [215] L. Farah, A. Haddouche, and A. Haddouche, "Comparison between proposed fuzzy logic and anfis for MPPT control for photovoltaic system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1065–1073, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp1065-1073.
- [216] M. S. Bin Tamrin and M. R. Ahmad, "Simulation of adaptive power management circuit for hybrid energy harvester and real-time sensing application," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 658–666, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp658-666.

- [217] Y. Y. Koay, J. D. Tan, S. P. Koh, K. H. Chong, S. K. Tiong, and J. Ekanayake, "Optimization of wind energy conversion systems – an artificial intelligent approach," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1040–1046, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i2.pp1040-1046.
- [218] A. Loubna, T. Riad, and M. Salima, "Standalone photovoltaic array fed induction motor driven water pumping system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 4534–4542, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp4534-4542.
- [219] M. O. Rachedi, M. L. Saidi, and F. Arbaoui, "MPPT control design for variable speed wind turbine," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 4604–4614, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp4604-4614.
- [220] B. Rached, M. Elharoussi, and E. Abdelmounim, "Design and investigations of MPPT strategies for a wind energy conversion system based on doubly fed induction generator," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 4770–4781, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp4770-4781.
- [221] J.-G. P.-Salado, L.-F. G.-Cárdenas, M.-A. R.-Licca, and F.-J. P.-Pinal, "Harvesting in electric vehicles: Combining multiple power tracking and fuel-cells," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5058–5073, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp5058-5073.
- [222] A. N. Hussain, A. J. Ali, and F. S. Ahmed, "Power quality improvement based on hybrid coordinated design of renewable energy sources for DC link channel DSTATCOM," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5108–5122, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp5108-5122.
- [223] A. P. Yoganandini and G. S. Anitha, "A modified particle swarm optimization algorithm to enhance MPPT in the PV array," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5001–5008, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp5001-5008.
- [224] A. G. Abdullah, M. S. Aziz, and B. A. Hamad, "Comparison between neural network and P&O method in optimizing MPPT control for photovoltaic cell," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5083–5092, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp5083-5092.
- [225] Z. Massa, A. Abounada, and M. Ramzi, "Robust non-linear control of a hybrid water pumping system based on induction motor," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1995–2006, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp1995-2006.
- [226] A. S. Badawi, N. F. Hasbullah, S. H. Yusoff, A. H. Hashim, and A. Zyoud, "Novel technique for hill climbing search to reach maximum power point tracking," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2019–2029, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp2019-2029.
- [227] H. Attia and K. Hossin, "Hybrid technique for an efficient PV system through intelligent MPPT and water cooling process," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1835–1843, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i4.pp1835-1843.
- [228] M. F. Zohra, B. Mokhtar, and M. Benyounes, "Sliding mode performance control applied to a DFIG system for a wind energy production," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6139–6152, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i6.pp6139-6152.
- [229] B. Amina, K. Mohammed, and M. B. Houari, "Super-twisting SMC for MPPT and grid-connected WECS based on SCIG," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 520–531, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i1.pp520-531.
- [230] K. Noussi, A. Abouloifa, H. Katir, I. Lachkar, and F. Giri, "Nonlinear control of grid-connected wind energy conversion system without mechanical variables measurements," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1139–1149, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1139-1149.
- [231] A. A. Adebisi, I. J. Lazarus, A. K. Saha, and E. E. Ojo, "Performance analysis of grid-tied photovoltaic system under varying weather condition and load," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 94–106, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i1.pp94-106.
- [232] N. Z. Laabidine, A. Errarhout, C. E. Bakkali, K. Mohammed, and B. Bossoufi, "Sliding mode control design of wind power generation system based on permanent magnet synchronous generator," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 393–403, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i1.pp393-403.
- [233] A. Ragab, M. I. Marei, M. Mokhtar, and A. Abdelsattar, "Design and performance evaluation of a pv interface system based on inductive power transfer," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 364–373, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i1.pp364-373.
- [234] J. Kumar, N. R. Parhyar, M. K. Panjwani, and D. Khan, "Design and performance analysis of PV grid-tied system with energy storage system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1077–1085, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i2.pp1077-1085.
- [235] B. Yu and S.-C. Ko, "Power dissipation analysis of PV module under partial shading," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1029–1035, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i2.pp1029-1035.
- [236] M. A. Beniss, H. El Moussaoui, T. Lamhamdi, and H. El Markhi, "Performance analysis and enhancement of direct power control of dfig based wind system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1034–1044, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1034-1044.
- [237] C. Abdeselem, A. Othmane, G. Brahim, S. M. Amine, H. Oussama, and H. M. Amine, "Power management strategy based sugeno fuzzy logic rules in an electric wheelchair," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1187–1195, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1187-1195.
- [238] Y. Abdelaziz, B. Abdelkrim, and M. Abdelkader, "Comparison between classical 'p&o' algorithm and flc of mppt for gpv under partial shading," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1131–1138, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1131-1138.
- [239] A. Ibnelouad, A. Elkari, H. Ayad, and M. Mjahed, "A neuro-fuzzy approach for tracking maximum power point of photovoltaic solar system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1252–1264, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp1252-1264.
- [240] M. Atig, Y. Miloud, A. Miloudi, and A. Merah, "A novel optimization of the particle swarm based maximum power point tracking for photovoltaic systems under partially shaded conditions," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1795–1803, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i3.pp1795-1803.
- [241] M. Fannakh, M. L. Elhafyani, S. Zouggar, and H. Zahboune, "Overall fuzzy logic control strategy of direct driven PMSG wind turbine connected to grid," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 5515–5529, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i6.pp5515-5529.

- [242] O. Bouchiba, T. Merizgui, B. Gaoui, S. Chettih, and A. Chekneane, "Artistic feasibility research on a standalone hybrid solar/wind system based on IncCond algorithm under variable load demands-a case study: South Algeria," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 4649–4658, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v11i6.pp4649-4658.
- [243] C. Hamid *et al.*, "Performance improvement of the variable speed wind turbine driving a DFIG using nonlinear control strategies," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2470–2482, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2470-2482.
- [244] M. E. Ahmad, A. H. Numan, and D. Y. Mahmood, "Enhancing performance of grid-connected photovoltaic systems based on three-phase five-level cascaded inverter," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2295–2304, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2295-2304.
- [245] R. Moutchou and A. Abbou, "Control of grid side converter in wind power based PMSG with PLL method," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2191–2200, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2191-2200.
- [246] A. Tariq and M. S. J. Asghar, "Development of an analog maximum power point tracker for photovoltaic panel," *2005 International Conference on Power Electronics and Drives Systems*, 2005, pp. 251–255, doi: 10.1109/PEDS.2005.1619694.
- [247] E. I. Ortiz-Rivera, "Maximum power point tracking using the optimal duty ratio for DC-DC converters and load matching in photovoltaic applications," *2008 Twenty-Third Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition*, 2008, pp. 987–991, doi: 10.1109/APEC.2008.4522841.
- [248] S. L. Brunton, C. W. Rowley, S. R. Kulkarni, and C. Clarkson, "Maximum power point tracking for photovoltaic optimization using ripple-based extremum seeking control," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 10, pp. 2531–2540, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2010.2049747.
- [249] K. Ding, X. Bian, H. Liu, and T. Peng, "A MATLAB-simulink-based PV module model and its application under conditions of nonuniform irradiance," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 864–872, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2012.2216529.
- [250] K. Sundareswaran, S. Peddapati, and S. Palani, "MPPT of PV systems under partial shaded conditions through a colony of flashing fireflies," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 463–472, June 2014, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2014.2298237.
- [251] L. L. Jiang, D. R. Nayanasiri, D. L. Maskell, and D. M. Vilathgamuwa, "A simple and efficient hybrid maximum power point tracking method for PV systems under partially shaded condition," *IECON 2013 - 39th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, 2013, pp. 1513–1518, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2013.6699357.
- [252] K. M. Tsang and W. L. Chan, "Maximum power point tracking for PV systems under partial shading conditions using current sweeping," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 93, pp. 249–258, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2015.01.029.
- [253] N. Hashim and Z. Salam, "Critical evaluation of soft computing methods for maximum power point tracking algorithms of photovoltaic systems," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 548–561, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10n1.pp548-561.
- [254] N. Priyadarshi, S. Padmanaban, J. B. Holm-Nielsen, M. S. Bhaskar, and F. Azam, "Internet of things augmented a novel PSO-employed modified zeta converter-based photovoltaic maximum power tracking system: hardware realisation," *IET Power Electronic*, vol. 13, no. 13, pp. 2775–2781, 2020, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2019.1121.
- [255] S. Mohanty, B. Subudhi, S. Member, and P. K. Ray, "A new MPPT design using grey wolf optimization technique for photovoltaic system under partial shading conditions," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2015, doi: 10.1109/TSTE.2015.2482120.
- [256] Y. Wang, Y. Li, and X. Ruan, "High-accuracy and fast-speed MPPT methods for PV string under partially shaded conditions," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 235–245, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2015.2465897.
- [257] A. Elkhateb, N. Abd Rahim, J. Selvaraj, and B. W. Williams, "DC-to-DC converter with low input current ripple for maximum photovoltaic power extraction," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 2246–2256, April 2015, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2014.2383999.
- [258] A. Anthon, Z. Zhang, and M. A. E. Andersen, "A high power boost converter for PV Systems operating up to 300 kHz using SiC devices," *2014 International Power Electronics and Application Conference and Exposition*, 2014, pp. 302–307, doi: 10.1109/PEAC.2014.7037872.
- [259] W. Li and X. He, "Review of nonisolated high-step-up DC/DC converters in photovoltaic grid-connected applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 1239–1250, April 2011, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2010.2049715.
- [260] E. O. Lindstrom, L. A. G. Rodriguez, A. R. Oliva, and J. C. Balda, "A novel method to compare converters for PV applications based on energy efficiency," *2014 Argentine Conference on Micro-Nanoelectronics, Technology and Applications (EAMTA)*, 2014, pp. 24–28, doi: 10.1109/EAMTA.2014.6906074.
- [261] P. F. de Melo, R. Gules, E. F. R. Romaneli, and R. C. Annunziato, "A modified SEPIC converter for high-power-factor rectifier and universal input voltage applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 310–321, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2009.2027323.
- [262] S. J. Chiang, H.-J. Shieh, and M.-C. Chen, "Modeling and control of PV charger system with SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 4344–4353, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2008.2005144.
- [263] M. H. Taghvaei, M. A. M. Radzi, S. M. Moosavain, H. Hizam, and M. Hamiruce Marhaban, "A current and future study on non-isolated DC–DC converters for photovoltaic applications," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 17, pp. 216–227, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.09.023.
- [264] M. E. Basoglu and B. Cakir, "Hardware based comparison of buck-boost converter topologies in MPPT systems," *2015 9th International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ELECO)*, 2015, pp. 1109–1112, doi: 10.1109/ELECO.2015.7394617.
- [265] S. J. Chiang, H. J. Shieh, and M. C. Chen, "Modeling and control of PV charger system with SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 4344–4353, Nov. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2008.2005144.
- [266] T. Kok Soon, S. Mekhilef, and A. Safari, "Simple and low cost incremental conductance maximum power point tracking using buck-boost converter," *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, vol. 5, no. 2, p. 23106, 2013, doi: 10.1063/1.4794749.
- [267] S. Bhattacharjee and B. J. Saharia, "A comparative study on converter topologies for maximum power point tracking application in photovoltaic generation," *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, vol. 6, no. 5, p. 53140, 2014, doi: 10.1063/1.4900579.
- [268] E. Mamarelis, G. Petrone, and G. Spagnuolo, "Design of a sliding-mode-controlled SEPIC for PV MPPT applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 3387–3398, July 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2013.2279361.
- [269] Y.-H. Kim, Y.-H. Ji, J.-G. Kim, Y.-C. Jung, and C.-Y. Won, "A new control strategy for improving weighted efficiency in photovoltaic AC module-type interleaved flyback inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 2688–2699, June 2013, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2012.2226753.

- [270] J. M. Enrique, E. Duran, M. Sidrach-de-Cardona, and J. M. Andujar, "Theoretical assessment of the maximum power point tracking efficiency of photovoltaic facilities with different converter topologies," *Solar Energy*, vol. 81, no. 1, pp. 31–38, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2006.06.006.
- [271] R. Rajesh and M. C. Mabel, "A comprehensive review of photovoltaic systems," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 51, pp. 231–248, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2015.06.006.
- [272] H.-L. Do, "Soft-switching SEPIC converter with ripple-free input current," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 2879–2887, June 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2175408.
- [273] S. Poshtkouhi, V. Palaniappan, M. Fard, and O. Trescases, "A general approach for quantifying the benefit of distributed power electronics for fine grained MPPT in photovoltaic applications using 3-D modeling," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 11, pp. 4656–4666, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2173353.
- [274] C. Hua and C. Shen, "Study of maximum power tracking techniques and control of DC/DC converters for photovoltaic power system," *PESC 98 Record. 29th Annual IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference (Cat. No.98CH36196)*, 1998, pp. 86–93 vol.1, doi: 10.1109/PESC.1998.701883.
- [275] R. Gules, W. M. Dos Santos, F. A. Dos Reis, E. F. R. Romaneli, and A. A. Badin, "A modified SEPIC converter with high static gain for renewable applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 5860–5871, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2013.2296053.
- [276] K. I. Hwu and Y. T. Yau, "Inductor-coupled KY boost converter," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 46, no. 24, p. 1624, 2010, doi: 10.1049/el.2010.2400.
- [277] R. Kumar and B. Singh, "Solar photovoltaic array fed Luo converter based BLDC motor driven water pumping system," *2014 9th International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems (ICIIS)*, 2014, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ICIINFS.2014.7036591.
- [278] A. Ghamrawi, J.-P. Gaubert, and D. Mehdi, "New control strategy for a quadratic boost converter used in solar energy system," *2016 IEEE International Energy Conference (ENERGYCON)*, 2016, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ENERGYCON.2016.7514125.
- [279] S. Sivakumar, M. J. Sathik, P. S. Manoj, and G. Sundararajan, "An assessment on performance of DC–DC converters for renewable energy applications," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 58, pp. 1475–1485, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2015.12.057.
- [280] A. Tomaszuk and A. Krupa, "High efficiency high step-up DC/DC converters—a review," *Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences: Technical Sciences*, pp. 475–483, 2011, doi: 10.2478/v10175-011-0059-1.
- [281] M. Z. Hossain and N. A. Rahim, "Recent progress and development on power DC-DC converter topology, control, design and applications: a review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 81, pp. 205–230, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.07.017.
- [282] S. Khosrogorji, M. Ahmadian, H. Torkaman, and S. Soori, "Multi-input DC/DC converters in connection with distributed generation units—a review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 66, pp. 360–379, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.07.023.
- [283] N. Zhang, D. Sutanto, and K. M. Muttaqi, "A review of topologies of three-port DC–DC converters for the integration of renewable energy and energy storage system," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 56, pp. 388–401, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2015.11.079.
- [284] G. Zhang, Z. Li, B. Zhang, and W. A. Halang, "Power electronics converters: past, present and future," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 81, pp. 2028–2044, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.290.
- [285] S. Sreejith and K. Balasubramanian, "Performance comparison of multi input capacitor converter circuits," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3471–3483, 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i5.pp3471-3483.
- [286] V. F. Pires, A. Cordeiro, D. Foito, and J. F. Silva, "High step-up DC–DC converter for fuel cell vehicles based on merged quadratic boost–Ćuk," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 8, pp. 7521–7530, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2019.2921851.
- [287] R. Gules, L. L. Pfitscher, and L. C. Franco, "An interleaved boost DC-DC converter with large conversion ratio," *2003 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (Cat. No. 03TH8692)*, 2003, pp. 411–416 vol. 1, doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2003.1267284.
- [288] P.-C. Huang, W.-Q. Wu, H.-H. Ho, K.-H. Chen, and G.-K. Ma, "High efficiency buck-boost converter with reduced average inductor current (RAIC) technique," *2009 Proceedings of ESSCIRC*, 2009, pp. 456–459, doi: 10.1109/ESSCIRC.2009.5326019.
- [289] J. Chen, D. Maksimović, and R. Erickson, "Buck-boost PWM converters having two independently controlled switches," *2001 IEEE 32nd Annual Power Electronics Specialists Conference (IEEE Cat. No.01CH37230)*, 2001, pp. 736–741 vol.2, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2001.954206.
- [290] R. Palanisamy, C. S. Boopathi, K. Selvakumar, and K. Vijayakumar, "Switching pulse generation for DC-DC boost converter using Xilinx-ISE with FPGA processor," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1722–1727, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp1722-1727.
- [291] N. Salehi, H. Martínez-García, and G. Velasco-Quesada, "Modified cascaded Z-Source high step-up boost converter," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 11, p. 1932, 2020, doi: 10.3390/electronics9111932.
- [292] R. Haroun, A. El Aroudi, A. Cid-Pastor, G. Garcia, C. Olalla, and L. Martinez-Salamero, "Impedance matching in photovoltaic systems using cascaded boost converters and sliding-mode control," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 3185–3199, June 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2339134.
- [293] E. Achille, T. Martiré, C. Glaize, and C. Joubert, "Optimized DC-AC boost converters for modular photovoltaic grid-connected generators," *2004 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics*, 2004, pp. 1005–1010 vol. 2, doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2004.1571951.
- [294] A. M. S. S. Andrade, R. C. Beltrame, L. Schuch, and M. L. da S. Martins, "Integrated quadratic-boost-Zeta converter for high voltage gain applications," *2014 11th IEEE/IAS International Conference on Industry Applications*, 2014, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/INDUSCON.2014.7059458.
- [295] M. Taufik, A. Nonaka, F. S. Huzayfa, R. M. Soedjono, and T. Taufik, "Effects of inductor current ripple on the performance of MPPT using boost converter," *2021 International Conference on Technology and Policy in Energy and Electric Power (ICT-PEP)*, 2021, pp. 202–207, doi: 10.1109/ICT-PEP53949.2021.9600919.
- [296] X. Sun, Y. Shen, Y. Zhu, and X. Guo, "Interleaved boost-integrated LLC resonant converter with fixed-frequency PWM control for renewable energy generation applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 8, pp. 4312–4326, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2358453.
- [297] H.-H. Wu, C.-L. Wei, Y.-C. Hsu, and R. B. Darling, "Adaptive peak-inductor-current-controlled PFM boost converter with a near-threshold startup voltage and high efficiency," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 1956–1965, April 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2323895.
- [298] F. Yang, X. Ruan, G. Wu, and Z. Ye, "Discontinuous-current mode operation of a two-phase interleaved boost DC–DC converter with coupled inductor," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 188–198, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2017.2669401.

- [299] Y. Yang, T. Guan, S. Zhang, W. Jiang, and W. Huang, "More symmetric four-phase inverse coupled inductor for low current ripples & high-efficiency interleaved bidirectional buck/boost converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 1952-1966, March 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2017.2745686.
- [300] R. M. Ariefianto, R. A. Aprilianto, H. Suryoatmojo, and S. Suwito, "Design and implementation of Z-Source inverter by simple boost control technique for laboratory scale micro-hydro power plant application," *Jurnal Teknik Elektro*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 62–70, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.15294/jte.v13i2.31884.
- [301] L. Huber and M. M. Jovanovic, "Design approach for server power supplies for networking applications," *APEC 2000. Fifteenth Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (Cat. No.00CH37058)*, 2000, pp. 1163-1169 vol.2, doi: 10.1109/APEC.2000.822834.
- [302] R. J. Wai and R. Y. Duan, "High-efficiency DC/DC converter with high voltage gain," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 354-364, Feb. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2006.888794.
- [303] B.-R. Lin and H.-H. Lu, "Single-phase three-level PWM rectifier," *Proceedings of the IEEE 1999 International Conference on Power Electronics and Drive Systems. PEDS'99 (Cat. No.99TH8475)*, 1999, pp. 63-68 vol.1, doi: 10.1109/PEDS.1999.794537.
- [304] H. Wu and X. He, "Single phase three-level power factor correction circuit with passive lossless snubber," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 946-953, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2002.805578.
- [305] W. Li and X. He, "A family of interleaved DC-DC converters deduced from a basic cell with winding-cross-coupled inductors (WCCIs) for high step-up or step-down conversions," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 1791-1801, July 2008, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2008.925204.
- [306] R. Haroun, A. El Aroudi, A. Cid-Pastor, G. Garfía, C. Olalla, and L. Martínez-Salamero, "Impedance matching in photovoltaic systems using cascaded boost converters and sliding-mode control," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 3185-3199, June 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2339134.
- [307] V. F. Pires, D. Foito, and J. F. Silva, "A single switch hybrid DC/DC converter with extended static gain for photovoltaic applications," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 146, pp. 228–235, 2017.
- [308] B. R. Lin, J. J. Chen, and S. F. Shen, "Zero voltage switching double-ended converter," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 187–196, 2010, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2008.0239.
- [309] A. E. Ibrahim, N. M. Nor, I. B. M. Nawi, M. F. Romlie, and K. N. M. Hasan, "Genetic algorithm to improve power output of photovoltaic system under partial shaded condition," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2182–2189, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i4.2182-2189.
- [310] I. D. Kim, J. Y. Kim, E. C. Nho, and H. G. Kim, "Analysis and design of a soft-switched PWM Sepic DC-DC converter," *Journal of Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 461–467, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.6113/JPE.2010.10.5.461.
- [311] B. Axelrod, Y. Berkovich, and A. Ioinovici, "Switched-capacitor/switched-inductor structures for getting transformerless hybrid DC-DC PWM converters," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 687-696, March 2008, doi: 10.1109/TCSI.2008.916403.
- [312] C. Yao, X. Ruan, and X. Wang, "Isolated buck-boost DC/DC converter for PV grid-connected system," *2010 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics*, 2010, pp. 889-894, doi: 10.1109/ISIE.2010.5637196.
- [313] B. Sahu and G. A. Rincón-Mora, "A low voltage, dynamic, noninverting, synchronous buck-boost converter for portable applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 443-452, March 2004, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2003.823196.
- [314] M. Ado, A. Jusoh, and T. Sutikno, "Asymmetric quasi impedance source buck-boost converter," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i2.pp2128-2138.
- [315] K. T. Ahmed, M. Datta, and N. Mohammad, "A novel two switch non-inverting buck-boost converter based maximum power point tracking system," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 3, no. 4, p. 467, 2013, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v3i4.2772.
- [316] M. R. Banaei and H. A. F. Bonab, "A high efficiency nonisolated buck-boost converter based on ZETA converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 1991-1998, March 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2019.2902785.
- [317] J.-K. Shiau, M. Y. Lee, Y.-C. Wei, and B.-C. Chen, "Circuit simulation for solar power maximum power point tracking with different buck-boost converter topologies," *Energies*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 5027–5046, 2014, doi: 10.3390/en7085027.
- [318] M. Veerachary, "Multi-input integrated buck-boost converter for photovoltaic applications," *2008 IEEE International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies*, 2008, pp. 546-551, doi: 10.1109/ICSET.2008.4747068.
- [319] A. Darwish, A. M. Massoud, D. Holliday, S. Ahmed, and B. W. Williams, "Single-stage three-phase differential-mode buck-boost inverters with continuous input current for PV applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 31, no. 12, pp. 8218-8236, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2016.2516255.
- [320] M. Orellana, S. Petibon, B. Estibals, and C. Alonso, "Four switch buck-boost converter for photovoltaic DC-DC power applications," *IECON 2010 - 36th Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, 2010, pp. 469-474, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2010.5674983.
- [321] V. Samavatian and A. Radan, "A high efficiency input/output magnetically coupled interleaved buck-boost converter with low internal oscillation for fuel-cell applications: Small signal modeling and dynamic analysis," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 67, pp. 261–271, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2014.11.011.
- [322] R. A. Aprilianto, E. Firmansyah, and F. D. Wijaya, "Review on control strategy for improving the interleaved converter performances," *2021 4th International Seminar on Research of Information Technology and Intelligent Systems, ISRITI 2021*, 2021, pp. 312–317, doi: 10.1109/ISRITI54043.2021.9702804.
- [323] V. Mummadi, "Multi-Input integrated buck-boost converter for photovoltaic applications," *2008 IEEE International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies, ICSET 2008*, 2008, pp. 546–551, doi: 10.1109/ICSET.2008.4747068.
- [324] J. Liao, J. Su, and L. Chang, "A single-phase transformer-less inverter with active decoupling," *2014 IEEE 5th International Symposium on Power Electronics for Distributed Generation Systems (PEDG)*, 2014, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/PEDG.2014.6878659.
- [325] Ö. Kircioğlu, M. Ünlü, and S. Çamur, "Modeling and analysis of DC-DC SEPIC converter with coupled inductors," *2016 International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (INDEL)*, 2016, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/INDEL.2016.7797807.
- [326] A. A. Fardoun, E. H. Ismail, A. J. Sabzali, and M. A. Al-Saffar, "New efficient bridgeless cuk rectifiers for PFC applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 3292-3301, July 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2182662.
- [327] H. S.-H. Chung, K. K. Tse, S. Y. R. Hui, C. M. Mok, and M. T. Ho, "A novel maximum power point tracking technique for solar panels using a SEPIC or Cuk converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 717-724, May 2003, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2003.810841.
- [328] E. Mamarelis, G. Petrone, and G. Spagnuolo, "Design of a sliding-mode-controlled SEPIC for PV MPPT applications," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 3387-3398, July 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2013.2279361.
- [329] C. G. Bianchin, R. Gules, A. A. Badin, and E. F. R. Romaneli, "High-power-factor rectifier using the modified SEPIC converter operating in discontinuous conduction mode," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 8, pp. 4349-4364, Aug. 2015,

- doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2360172.
- [330] A. Jaafar, P. Lefranc, E. Godoy, X. L. Shi, A. Fayaz, and N. Li, "Experimental validation with a control point of view analysis of the SEPIC converter," *2009 35th Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics*, 2009, pp. 462-497, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2009.5414966.
- [331] J. Hu, A. D. Sagneri, J. M. Rivas, Y. Han, S. M. Davis, and D. J. Perreault, "High-frequency resonant SEPIC converter with wide input and output voltage ranges," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 189-200, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2149543.
- [332] M. Veerachary, "Power tracking for nonlinear PV sources with coupled inductor SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 1019-1029, July 2005, doi: 10.1109/TAES.2005.1541446.
- [333] V. Eng, U. Pinsopon, and C. Bunlaksananusorn, "Modeling of a SEPIC converter operating in continuous conduction mode," *2009 6th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology*, 2009, pp. 136-139, doi: 10.1109/ECTICON.2009.5136982.
- [334] E. Babaei and M. E. S. Mahmoodieh, "Calculation of output voltage ripple and design considerations of SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 1213-1222, March 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2013.2262748.
- [335] N. Mohammad, M. Quamruzzaman, M. R. T. Hossain, and M. R. Alam, "Parasitic effects on the performance of DC-DC SEPIC in photovoltaic maximum power point tracking applications," *Smart Grid and Renewable Energy*, vol. 04, no. 01, pp. 113-121, 2013, doi: 10.4236/sgre.2013.41014.
- [336] V. Eng and C. Bunlaksananusorn, "Modeling of a SEPIC converter operating in discontinuous conduction mode," *2009 6th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology*, 2009, pp. 140-143, doi: 10.1109/ECTICON.2009.5136983.
- [337] A. S. Taiwo and J. Y. Oricha, "Modeling, Steady-state Analysis of a SEPIC DC-DC converter based on switching Function and harmonic balance technique," *Journal of Power and Energy Engineering*, vol. 02, no. 04, pp. 704-711, 2014, doi: 10.4236/jpee.2014.24094.
- [338] M. A. Al-Saffar, E. H. Ismail, A. J. Sabzali, and A. A. Fardoun, "An improved topology of SEPIC converter with reduced output voltage ripple," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 2377-2386, Sept. 2008, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2008.2001916.
- [339] O. Kircioğlu, M. Ünlü, and S. Camur, "Modeling and analysis of DC-DC SEPIC converter with coupled inductors," *2016 International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (INDEL)*, 2016, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/INDEL.2016.7797807.
- [340] B. Axelrod, Y. Berkovich, S. Tapuchi, and A. Ioinovici, "Steep conversion ration Ćuk, Zeta, and sepic converters based on a switched coupled-inductor cell," *2008 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference*, 2008, pp. 3009-3014, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2008.4592410.
- [341] K. Nathan, S. Ghosh, Y. Siwakoti, and T. Long, "A new DC-DC converter for photovoltaic systems: coupled-inductors combined Ćuk-SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 191-201, March 2019, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2018.2876454.
- [342] S.-Y. Yu, R. Zhao, and A. Kwasinski, "Design considerations of a multiple-input isolated single ended primary inductor converter (SEPIC) for distributed generation sources," *2011 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition*, 2011, pp. 3960-3967, doi: 10.1109/ECCE.2011.6064308.
- [343] A. El Khateb, N. A. Rahim, J. Selvaraj, and M. N. Uddin, "Fuzzy-logic-controller-based SEPIC converter for maximum power point tracking," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 2349-2358, July-Aug. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2014.2298558.
- [344] M. Quamruzzaman, N. Mohammad, M. A. Matin, and M. R. Alam, "Highly efficient maximum power point tracking using DC-DC coupled inductor single-ended primary inductance converter for photovoltaic power systems," *International Journal of Sustainable Energy*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 914-932, 2016, doi: 10.1080/14786451.2014.961922.
- [345] P. F. De Melo, R. Gules, E. F. R. Romaneli, and R. C. Annunziato, "A modified SEPIC converter for high-power-factor rectifier and universal input voltage applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 310-321, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2009.2027323.
- [346] Z. Chen, "PI and sliding mode control of a Ćuk converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 3695-3703, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2012.2183891.
- [347] T. M. K. Faistel, R. A. Guisso, A. M. S. S. Andrade, and M. L. da Silva Martins, "Comparative evaluation of a family of isolated Ćuk DC/DC converter with step-up techniques," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 16, pp. 3637-3650, 2020, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2020.0151.
- [348] A. M. S. S. Andrade, T. M. K. Faistel, A. Toebe, and R. A. Guisso, "Family of transformerless active switched inductor and switched capacitor Ćuk DC-DC converter for high voltage gain applications," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 390-398, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JESTIE.2021.3091419.
- [349] H. Li, L. Cheng, X. Sun, and C. Li, "High step-up combined boost-Ćuk converter with switched-inductor," *IET Power Electronics*, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1049/pe12.12335.
- [350] F. Baptista, A. Silva, and F. Pires, "Boost/Ćuk converter using a single controlled power semiconductor for photovoltaic applications," *Energies*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1-10, 2021.
- [351] R. Kumar and B. Singh, "Solar PV powered BLDC motor drive for water pumping using Ćuk converter," *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 222-232, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1049/iet-epa.2016.0328.
- [352] M. Zhu and F. L. Luo, "Enhanced self-lift Ćuk converter for negative-to-positive voltage conversion," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 9, pp. 2227-2233, Sept. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2010.2047269.
- [353] S.-W. Lee, S.-R. Lee, and C.-H. Jeon, "A new high efficient Bi-directional DC/DC converter in the dual voltage system," *Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 343-350, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.5370/JEET.2006.1.3.343.
- [354] A. Elmelegi, M. Aly, and E. M. Ahmed, "Developing phase-shift PWM-based distributed MPPT technique for photovoltaic systems," *Proceedings of 2019 International Conference on Innovative Trends in Computer Engineering, ITCE 2019*, Feb. 2019, pp. 492-497, doi: 10.1109/ITCE.2019.8646399.
- [355] E. Durán, J. M. Andújar, F. Segura, and A. J. Barragán, "A high-flexibility DC load for fuel cell and solar arrays power sources based on DC-DC converters," *Applied Energy*, vol. 88, no. 5, pp. 1690-1702, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.11.002.
- [356] P. Valencia and C. Ramos-Paja, "Sliding-mode controller for maximum power point tracking in grid-connected photovoltaic systems," *Energies*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 12363-12387, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.3390/en8112318.
- [357] G. Jiménez-Castillo, F. J. Muñoz-Rodríguez, C. Rus-Casas, and P. Gómez-Vidal, "Improvements in performance analysis of photovoltaic systems: Array power monitoring in pulse width modulation charge controllers," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 19, no. 9, 2019, doi: 10.3390/s19092150.

- [358] Y. Yang, J. Ma, C. N.-M. Ho, and Y. Zou, "A new coupled-inductor structure for interleaving bidirectional DC-DC converters," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 841-849, Sept. 2015, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2015.2443178.
- [359] Y. Yang, T. Guan, S. Zhang, W. Jiang, and W. Huang, "More symmetric four-phase inverse coupled inductor for low current ripples & high-efficiency interleaved bidirectional buck/boost converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 1952-1966, March 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2017.2745686.
- [360] S. Kimura, S. Aoto, M. Ishihara, J. Imaoka, and M. Yamamoto, "Interleaved active clump forward converter with novel integrated magnetic components," *2015 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, 2015, pp. 6029-6036, doi: 10.1109/ECCE.2015.7310505.
- [361] K. Nathan, S. Ghosh, Y. Siwakoti, and T. Long, "A new DC-DC converter for photovoltaic systems: coupled-inductors combined cuk-SEPIC converter," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 191-201, March 2019, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2018.2876454, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 191-201, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TEC.2018.2876454.
- [362] B.-R. Lin and J.-J. Chen, "Analysis of an integrated flyback and zeta converter with active clamping technique," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 355-363, 2009, doi: 10.1049/iet-pel.2008.0038.
- [363] N. Valsalan and S. T. Subha, "Dual zeta converter with reduced ripple for sensitive load applications," *2013 International Conference on Energy Efficient Technologies for Sustainability*, 2013, pp. 1195-1200, doi: 10.1109/ICEETS.2013.6533557.
- [364] S. Arfin, A. Al Mamun, T. Chowdhury, and G. Sarowar, "Zeta based hybrid DC-DC converter using switched inductor and switched capacitor combined structure for high gain applications," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Power, Electrical, and Electronics and Industrial Applications (PEEIACON)*, 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/PEEIACON48840.2019.9071940.
- [365] M. R. Banaei and H. A. F. Bonab, "A high efficiency nonisolated buck-boost converter based on ZETA converter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 1991-1998, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2019.2902785.
- [366] S. Mohammadsalehian, F. Sedaghati, R. Eskandari, H. Shayeghi, and E. S. Asl, "A modified double input z-source dc-dc converter for standalone PV/Battery system application," *2020 11th Power Electronics, Drive Systems, and Technologies Conference (PEDSTC)*, 2020, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/PEDSTC49159.2020.9088453.
- [367] L. Yang, D. Qiu, B. Zhang, G. Zhang, and W. Xiao, "A modified Z-source DC-DC converter," *2014 16th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications*, 2014, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/EPE.2014.6910751.
- [368] B. Poorali, H. M. Jazi, and E. Adib, "Improved high step-up Z-source DC-DC converter with single core and ZVT operation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 11, pp. 9647-9655, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2017.2787907.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Tole Sutikno is a lecturer in Electrical Engineering Department at the Universitas Ahmad Dahlan (UAD), Yogyakarta, Indonesia. He received his B.Eng., M.Eng. and Ph.D. degrees in Electrical Engineering from Universitas Diponegoro, Universitas Gadjah Mada and Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, in 1999, 2004 and 2016, respectively. He has been an Associate Professor in UAD, Yogyakarta, Indonesia since 2008. He is currently an Editor-in-Chief of the TELKOMNIKA and the Head of the Embedded Systems and Power Electronics Research Group (ESPERG). His research interests include the field of digital design, industrial applications, industrial electronics, industrial informatics, power electronics, motor drives, renewable energy, FPGA applications, embedded system, artificial intelligence, intelligent control, information technology and digital library. He can be contacted at email: tole@te.uad.ac.id.

Hendril Satrian Purnama received his B.Eng. degree in Electrical Engineering from Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia in 2017. After receiving his degree, he became a member of the Embedded Systems and Power Electronics Research Group (ESPERG), and worked there as a researcher. In addition, he is also active as assistant editor in several international journals in the field of electrical engineering, computer and informatics. His research interests include power electronics, renewable energy technology, robotics and the Internet of Things. He can be contacted at email: lfriyan220@gmail.com.

Rizky Ajie Aprilianto is currently a researcher at the Embedded System and Power Electronics Research Group (ESPERG), Indonesia. He received a bachelor's degree from the Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Negeri Semarang, Indonesia, in 2018 and a master's degree from the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia, in 2022. His research interests include power electronics, SMPS, DC-DC Converters, PV systems, and energy management, planning, and integrating renewable energy power plants. He can be contacted at email: rizkyajiea@gmail.com

Awang Jusoh received B.Eng. in Electrical and Electronic Engineering from Brighton Polytechnic, the UK, in 1985, the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degree in power electronics and electrical engineering from the University of Birmingham, the UK, in 1995 and 2004. He is an Associate Professor with the Department of Electrical Power Engineering, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia. His research interests are in the control of power electronics systems, DC–DC converters, energy conversion, and renewable energy. He can be contacted at email: awang@fke.utm.my.

Nuryono Satya Widodo received his B.Eng. and M.Eng. degrees in Electrical Engineering from Universitas Gadjah Mada in 2000 and 2015, respectively. He is a Senior Lecturer with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Currently, he is pursuing a PhD degree at Sepuluh Nopember Institute of Technology (ITS). His current research interests include robotics, automation, control, electric vehicle and renewable energy. He can be contacted at email: nuryono.sw@ee.uad.ac.id.

Budi Santosa received Doktorandus (Drs) in Mechanical Engineering Education and Masters and PhD in Vocational Technology Education from the State University of Yogyakarta in 1985, 2022, and 2014, respectively. He is a Senior Lecturer with the Department of Vocational Teacher Education, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. His current research interests include vocational research; android-based systems; automotives; electric vehicles; and renewable energy. He can be contacted by email at: budi.santosa@mpv.uad.ac.id.